

The logo for OPTAMUS is displayed in blue, with the letter 'O' containing a power button symbol. Below the logo is a stylized illustration of a city skyline with various buildings and trees, rendered in shades of gray.

OPTAMUS

OPTIMISING
ENERGY USE IN
CITIES THROUGH
SMART DECISION
SUPPORT SYSTEMS

FP7/608703

Inference engine integrated in the management environments

Deliverable 3.3

This document has been prepared within the framework of the European project “OPTIMising the energy USE in cities with smart decision support system (OPTIMUS)” co-financed by the European Commission through the “Seventh Framework (FP7)” Programme (Grant agreement no 608703).

Start date of the project: October 2013

End date of the project: September 2016

Deliverable no: 3.3

Deliverable title: Inference engine integrated in the management environment

Key authors: Alfonso Capozzoli (POLITO), Vincenzo Corrado (POLITO), Haris Doukas (NTUA), Alice Gorrino (POLITO), Leandro Madrazo (FUNITEC), Álvaro Sicilia (FUNITEC)

Editors: Alfonso Capozzoli (POLITO), Alice Gorrino (POLITO)

Project Partners:

For further information visit:

www.optimus-smartcity.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Seventh Framework Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under grant agreement no 608703

The sole responsibility for the content of this publication lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Preface

This report is prepared within the framework of the OPTIMUS – OPTIMising the energy USE in cities with smart decision support system (OPTIMUS) (608703), supported by the 7th Framework Programme, under the Objective ICT-2013.6.4 Optimising Energy Systems in Smart Cities. OPTIMUS aims to design, develop and implementation a Decision Support System (DSS) addressed to city authorities, in order to assist them to optimize the energy use in their premises and reduce CO₂ emissions.

Summary

This deliverable refers to Task 3.3 of the project, which is part of Work Package 3.

The general purpose of WP3 is the construction of the OPTIMUS DSS architecture. Task 3.3 has the main purpose to develop and implement the intelligent rules for the energy optimization based on data that the DSS receives as input, both from the capturing modules and from the data mining process as described in D3.2.

Deliverable structure

This deliverable has the following structure:

- Description of the inference rules
- Application of the inference rules

The first section contains the description of the methodology while the second section goes deeper into the application and the implementation of the rules in the inference engine.

CONTENTS

1	Introduction	4
1.1	Goals of the deliverable	4
1.2	General content of the deliverable	4
1.3	Interconnection between tasks	5
2	Description of the inference rules	6
2.1	Theoretical description of the inference rules.....	6
2.2	Specific description of the analysed inference rules.....	6
2.3	Inference Rule 1: Rationalizing the displacement of the occupants	8
2.3.1	General structure and involved variables.....	8
2.3.2	Classification tree and engineering model	9
2.3.3	Optimization criteria.....	11
2.3.4	Description of the inference rule	12
2.4	Inference Rule 2: Determination of the neutral temperature through Thermal Comfort Validation (TCV).....	15
2.4.1	General structure and involved variables.....	15
2.4.2	Optimization criteria.....	15
2.4.3	Description of the inference rule	16
2.5	Inference Rule 3: Determination of the preferred temperature according to adaptive comfort model	19
2.5.1	General structure and involved variables.....	19
2.5.2	Optimization criteria.....	19
2.5.3	Description of the inference rule	20
2.6	Inference Rule 4: Determination of the optimum start/stop of the heating system.....	22
2.6.1	General structure and involved variables.....	22
2.6.2	Optimization criteria.....	23
2.6.3	Description of the inference rule	23
2.7	Inference Rule 5: Assessing free cooling options	26
2.7.1	General structure and involved variables.....	26
2.7.2	Optimization criteria.....	26
2.7.3	Description of the inference rule	27
2.8	Inference Rule 6: Evaluating the electricity production of the PV system to check possible faults	30
2.8.1	General structure and involved variables.....	30

2.8.2	Optimization criteria.....	30
2.8.3	Description of the inference rule	30
2.9	Inference Rule 7: Shifting electrical loads to optimize PV performance.....	34
2.9.1	General structure and involved variables.....	35
2.9.2	Optimization criteria.....	36
2.9.3	Description of the inference rule	36
2.9.4	Nomenclature.....	42
2.10	Inference Rule 8: Determination of the energy source to cover the demand, considering battery charging, RES production and the grid	43
2.10.1	General structure and involved variables.....	43
2.10.2	Optimization criteria.....	44
2.10.3	Impact of the inference rule to SCEAF indicators	44
2.10.4	Description of the inference rule	45
2.11	Inference Rule 9: Peak shaving towards energy cost optimization.....	48
2.11.1	General structure and involved variables.....	48
2.11.2	Optimization criteria.....	49
2.11.3	Description of the inference rule	50
3	Application of the Inference Rules: Action Plans.....	53
3.1	Action Plan 1: Scheduling and management of the occupancy.....	53
3.1.1	Description of data and building partitioning	53
3.1.2	Application to a case study.....	55
3.1.3	Impact of the action plan to the SCEAF indicators.....	58
3.2	Action Plan 2: Scheduling the set point temperature.....	60
3.3	Scheduling the set point temperature through Thermal Comfort Validation	61
3.3.1	Description of data and building partitioning	61
3.3.2	Application to a case study.....	62
3.4	Scheduling the set point temperature according to the adaptive comfort concept.....	69
3.4.1	Description of data and building partitioning	69
3.4.2	Application to a case study.....	69
3.4.3	Impact of the action plan to the SCEAF indicators.....	70
3.5	Action Plan 3: Scheduling the on/off of the heating system.....	72
3.5.1	Description of data and building partitioning	72
3.5.2	Application to a case study.....	74
3.5.3	Impact of the action plan to the SCEAF indicators.....	76
3.6	Action Plan 4: Management of the air-side economizer	78

3.6.1	Description of data and building partitioning	78
3.6.2	Application to a case study	79
3.6.3	Impact of the action plan to the SCEAF indicators.....	81
3.7	Action Plan 5: Scheduling the PV maintenance	82
3.7.1	Description of data and building partitioning	82
3.7.2	Application to a case study.....	83
3.7.3	Impact of the action plan to the SCEAF indicators.....	84
3.8	Action Plan 6: Scheduling of the sale/consumption of the electricity produced through the PV system	86
3.8.1	Description of data and building partitioning	86
3.8.2	Application to a case study.....	86
3.8.3	Impact of the action plan to the SCEAF indicators.....	94
3.9	Action Plan 7: Scheduling the battery use towards peak shaving and energy cost optimization.....	96
3.9.1	Description of data and building partitioning	96
3.9.2	Application to a case study.....	100
3.9.3	Impact of the action plan to the SCEAF indicators.....	101
4	Inference rules implementation.....	103
4.1	Implementation of a inference rule as a Rapidminer process.....	103
4.2	Implementation of the inference rule as PHP classes	104
5	Nomenclature.....	105
6	References.....	106

1 Introduction

This report describes the current status of T3.3.

The main purpose of D3.3 is to describe the development and implementation of the inference rules based on the data that the DSS will receive as input in combination with the data mining output described in D3.2.

The document describes the inference rule process, from the input data needed, to the inference rule theoretical definition, for each DSS action to be implemented.

For each action, the following information is reported: the general structure and the involved variables; the indicators to be optimized; the description of the inference rule.

1.1 Goals of the deliverable

The deliverable summarises the outcomes of Task 3.3 *Inference Rules*, which is part of Work Package 3 *Semantic Data Integration and Development of OPTIMUS DSS*.

The main goal of the deliverable is to develop and implement all the knowledge and intelligent rules for the energy optimization and to realize the inference engine.

The specific goals of the deliverable are the followings:

- Defining the inference rules needed for the implementation of the suggested actions
- Developing the inference rules using the available data coming from both the capturing modules and the data mining process
- Implementing the inference rules in the inference engine

1.2 General content of the deliverable

The deliverable is divided into two main sections: the first one contains the description of the inference rules while the second section contains their application.

In the first section, each inference rule is connected to a suggested action as listed in D2.1 and it is described according to the following sub-sections:

- General structure and involved variables. This sub-section describes the general structure of the scenario modelling starting from the input data needed, both from capturing modules and data mining process, to the inference rule process. Each input datum is characterized by its attributes as described in D2.1
- Indicators to be optimized. This sub-section describes the optimization criteria considered together with the indicators that are going to be optimized according to the approach described in D2.1.
- Description of the inference rule. This sub-section contains the theoretical description of the inference rule.

In the second section the application of each inference rule to the pilot buildings is presented. The following sub-sections are identified:

- Description of data for the development of the inference engine. This sub-section contains the detailed description of the input data coming from each pilot building involved in the scenario modelling together with the building partitioning criteria according to the procedure described in D2.1.
- Application of the inference rule. This sub-section presents the testing of the methodology described in the previous section together with the main outcomes.
- Implementation of the inference rule in the DSS engine. This sub-section contains the technical description of the implementation of the inference rules as PHP classes.

1.3 Interconnection between tasks

The work carried out in Task 3.3 is related to other tasks in the following way:

- Task 2.2 – 2.6 (Capturing modules) output deals with the dynamic input data of Task 3.3
- Task 3.2 (Data mining analysis) outputs are the input data of Task 3.3. In particular, predicted data from data mining analysis are the input data of the inference rules.
- Task 3.3 outputs are the input data of Task 3.4 (Front-End Environment).
- Task 3.5 integrates the different components of the DSS including the inferences rules.

2 Description of the inference rules

2.1 Theoretical description of the inference rules

An inference rule is an expert knowledge-based rule that can be expressed in a logical form (if-then), with a graphic expression (flow-chart, table etc.) or as a mathematical equation.

The inference rule process is a part of the scenario modelling that allows to elaborate the action plan suggested by the DSS.

Each suggested action is obtained through a modelling process starting from the capturing of the static and dynamic data, the prediction modelling process (through data mining techniques and grey model approach) and the inference rules.

Inference rules are structured either as logical functions containing premises and conclusions (e.g. if ... then ...) or as mathematical models. The inference rules are able to describe the system (building, technical systems etc.) a priori on the basis of an expert knowledge and provide the optimization criteria for a specific action.

2.2 Specific description of the analysed inference rules

The inference rules are associated with specific suggested actions. Starting from the general list of suggested actions elaborated in D2.1, the set of actions to be implemented in the inference engine is shown in Figure 1 together with the correlation between inference rules and action plans.

Figure 2 shows the connection among action plans. The scheduling and management of the occupancy influences the management of the heating and cooling system, both in terms of HVAC start/stop and set point temperature scheduling. Moreover, the occupancy management directly influences the air conditioning management, because the action plan 4 contains the possibility to activate demand control ventilation as a function of the occupancy profile. Also the system operation is connected to the management of the air side economizer since the input data for the management of the economizer are both the set point temperature of a zone and the on/off switching of the system. The energy demand of the building zone affects the action plan 6, that allows to schedule the sale/consumption of the electricity produced through the PV system and to suggest as output the load shifting. The output of this rule in term of load shifting affects ultimately the occupancy management.

SYSTEM CLASSIFICATION

ACTION PLANS

INFERENCE RULES

Figure 1. Classification of the DSS suggested Action Plans in correspondence with Inference Rules

Figure 2. Connection among action plans

2.3 Inference Rule 1: Rationalizing the displacement of the occupants

This action is aimed at reducing the building energy consumption through the optimal zone assignment for occupants considering the use of the minimum number of thermal zones, the ranking of energy request for each of them, the predicted thermal comfort and the occupant's profiles. The application of the inference rule allows to reduce the building energy use considering the HVAC start/stop schedule based on the occupied thermal zones and occupancy profile. The heating/cooling system could be turned off when the zones are estimated to be empty or could be turned on according to the estimated occupancy profile (e.g. when the occupants enter the zone). Moreover, since the zones may have different occupancy patterns, the occupants with similar profiles or similar job tasks may be located in the same zones to unify the start/stop times.

2.3.1 General structure and involved variables

The general structure of the scenario modelling is shown in Figure 3. Both static and dynamic data are needed for its implementation. The data from social media capturing module are involved together with static data related to the building zones.

As regards the static data, each zone to be managed separately from the rest of the building, requires information about the estimated occupancy and energy need for both space heating and cooling.

To estimate the energy consumption of each thermal zone and introduce an energy ranking for each of them, an engineering model is considered as explained in section 2.3.2.2.

Moreover, to estimate the occupancy profile for a standard week, an elaboration process based on a CART (Classification and Regression Tree) algorithm is used as explained in section 2.3.2.1.

Figure 3. General structure of the action plan

In Table 1 a detailed list of the input variables both static and dynamic needed for the modelling process is shown together with their attributes.

Table 1. Listing of input variables

Input variable		Observed/ predicted	Time aggregation	Spatial scale
Occupancy (occupants)	Number of occupants	Observed	Hourly	Building zone
		Estimated	Daily	Building
	Number of hours present	Observed	Hourly	Building zone
		Predicted	Daily	Building zone
Constraints	Predicted	Daily	Building zone	
Zone orientation	-	-	-	Building zone
Compactness factor	-	-	-	Building zone
Climatic data	Outdoor air temperature/Total solar radiation	Observed/ Predicted	Hourly	-
Energy generation system	Energy consumption	Observed/ Predicted	Hourly	Building zone
Thermal comfort	Indoor air temperature	Observed	Hourly	Building zone

2.3.2 Classification tree and engineering model

2.3.2.1 Classification tree

Knowledge about occupancy prediction provides valuable information both on building and electricity grid level. On building level, occupancy prediction could give information support for automated building energy management, real-time calculation of building energy flexibility and precise real-time energy efficient operation and planning.

A CART algorithm is a sequential binary decision tree to be “grown” by splitting a parent node into two child nodes repeatedly, beginning with the root node that contains the whole learning sample. The CART may easily handle both numerical and categorical variables. Initially, all records in the training data are grouped together into a single unit. At each iteration, the algorithm chooses a predictor attribute that can best separate the target class values, and measures of impurity are employed to estimate the ability of a predictor to separate the target class values. The CART was developed using the number of occupants as dependent variable of the analysis. The categorical predictor attributes are the weekdays and the parts of the day. In particular the CART provides an estimated average number of occupants for each part of day within each day of the week ahead. The five parts of the day selected are: early morning (6.00– 9.00 a.m.), morning (9.00-13.00), afternoon (13.00-17.00), late afternoon (17.00-20.00), night (20.00-6.00). In Figure 4 a typical output of the CART is shown. In order to interpret the results of the classification, different final nodes are highlighted. In particular the Morning and Afternoon final nodes provide information about the expected total number of occupants for each day. As described in the following section the estimated daily total number of the occupants is used to determine the minimum number of the thermal zones that will be occupied during the day. Moreover Early morning and Late afternoon final node are used to establish the HVAC start/stop schedule. The final nodes in

which the expected number of occupants is zero represent the parts of the day in which the building can be considered unoccupied and the air conditioning system does not work.

Figure 4. Example of the CART

2.3.2.2 Methodology for the estimation of the energy need for space heating and cooling

A simplified white model is used to estimate the energy need for space heating and cooling of each building zone subjected to the action. It is a monthly steady state model according to EN ISO 13790:2008. According to the methodology, the energy need for space heating

($Q_{H,nd}$) and cooling ($Q_{C,nd}$) is calculated for each thermal zone that can be managed separately from the rest of the building.

The seasonal energy need for heating and cooling of each zone is pre-calculated and associated with each building zone as a static datum in the DSS. This calculation procedure allows to list the building zones with their growing energy need, for space heating and cooling separately.

According to the building parameters reported in D2.1, the following building features are needed to calculate the simplified energy need for each thermal zone:

- Building use (office, educational, etc.)
- Geometry of each conditioned zone (gross floor area, net floor area, gross volume, net volume, external dimension of the thermal envelope area)
- Thermal characteristics of the opaque envelope (thermal transmittance)
- Thermal and solar characteristics of windows and type of the solar shading device if present

As regards the climatic data, the monthly values of outdoor air temperature and solar irradiance for different orientations are needed.

The energy needs both heating and cooling refer to standard condition. The following assumptions are made:

- Continuous heating and cooling mode
- Length of heating and cooling seasons calculated according to EN 13790
- Fixed set points for heating and cooling
- Ventilation air flows calculated according to EN 15241 and EN 15242
- Internal heat gains set according to EN ISO 13790 as a function of the building use
- Management of the shading device set according to EN ISO 13790

2.3.3 Optimization criteria

A control strategy based on actual occupancy might improve HVAC system related energy efficiency. Accurate occupancy profiles are important to determine actual energy demands and corresponding control schedules.

The rule is aimed at displacing the building occupants in order to occupy the minimum number of thermal zones according to their maximum capacity and, when it is possible, considering the building zones with the lowest estimated energy consumption or the zones characterized by a higher thermal comfort. The thermal comfort evaluation is based on the feedback from the occupants through the TCV application as explained in section 2.1.

The optimization criteria are therefore the minimization of the energy consumption of the building, by controlling the on/off schedule of the heating/cooling system of the building zones, while taking into account the feedback of the building occupants through social media.

The parameters to be optimized are:

- energy consumption
- CO₂ emissions
- thermal comfort

2.3.4 Description of the inference rule

The inference rule process consists of logical rules aimed at defining the building zones to be occupied the week ahead. Specifically, the building zones firstly occupied are the ones that allow to optimize both energy consumption and thermal comfort requirements.

In the following, a description of the inference rule is presented.

1. Record the following input data for a period of at least one week:
 - Predicted energy consumption on an hourly basis for each building zone coming from the application of the engineering model.
 - Feedback from social media module for each building zone
 - Estimated occupancy by means of the classification tree: daily maximum number of occupants in the whole building, arrival time, duration of stay and departure time for the entire building
 - Constraints for each building zone: binary information (yes/no) describing the presence/absence of scheduled appointments (e.g. meetings)
2. For each building zone, set the maximum capacity (e.g maximum number of occupants)
3. Aggregate/disaggregate the input data above mentioned (except from the predicted occupancy that can be referred to the entire building) to have the same spatial scale
4. Aggregate both the energy consumption and the thermal comfort indexes into average daily values
5. Order the zones with an increasing predicted energy consumption
6. Order the zones with decreasing thermal comfort
7. List the zones with constraints (events that can't be moved)
8. Propose to displace occupants according to the sequence described in Figure 5. Zones that need to be occupied first are those with constraints, with the lowest predicted energy consumption index and the greater predicted thermal comfort index. According to the indicator to be optimized, a priority is given to minimizing the energy consumption or, alternatively, to maximizing the occupants comfort.

Zone number	Constraints	Predicted energy consumption	Predicted thermal comfort
Zone 4	Yes	↓ <i>Increasing</i>	↑ <i>Decreasing</i>
Zone 1	Yes		
Zone 2	No		
Zone 3	No		

Figure 5. Criteria for occupying the building zones

The inference rule is based on a hierarchical process for the zone assignment. In particular two levels in the inference rule are evaluated, meaning after the primary rule is satisfied, the secondary rule is taken into consideration. If there is a conflict between the two sets of rules, primary rule given the priority. In the inference rule, the primary rule is set for zone capacity. The primary rule provides the occupation of the minimum number of the thermal zones when the daily maximum number of occupants predicted is lower than the sum of the capacity of the largest zones in the building. The secondary rule ensure that the occupants occupy the thermal zones following the energy ranking.

In the case of three thermal zones (in the table below is provided an example), the inference rules are described in the following:

	Max Capacity [n° occ.]	Energy ranking
Zone 1	437	2
Zone 2	454	1
Zone 3	491	3
Tot	1382	

- If daily total maximum estimated number of occupants is higher than the sum of the capacity of the two largest zones then three zones will be occupied during the day according to the zone energy ranking (or to thermal comfort).
- If daily total maximum estimated number of occupants is higher than the capacity of the largest zone but lower of the sum of two zones, then 2 zones will be occupied during the day according to the zone energy ranking (or to thermal comfort)
- If daily total maximum estimated number of occupants is lower than the capacity of at least one of the three zones then occupy this zone without considering its energy rank.
- If daily total maximum estimated number of occupants is lower than the capacity of more than one zone then occupy the zone with the best energy rank.

If constraints exist only in one zone

- If daily total maximum estimated number of occupants is higher than the capacity of the zone with constraints but lower of the sum of this zone with only one of the other zones, then 2 zones will be occupied during the day. In particular the zone with constraints and the zone that verify this hypothesis. If more than one zone verify the previous hypothesis then will be occupied during the day the zone with constraints and the zone with best energy rank.

- If daily total maximum estimated number of occupants is lower than the capacity of the zone with constraints then occupy this zone without considering its energy rank.

If constraints exist in two zone

- If daily total maximum estimated number of occupants is higher than the sum of the capacity of the two zones with constraints then three zones will be occupied during the day.
- If daily total maximum estimated number of occupants is lower than the sum of the capacity of the zones with constraints then occupy these zones.

If constraints exist in all the zones

In this case the HVAC will work in all the zones and the start/stop schedule will be set according to occupancy profiles.

2.4 Inference Rule 2: Determination of the neutral temperature through Thermal Comfort Validation (TCV)

2.4.1 General structure and involved variables

Set-point management is applied in municipal buildings, aiming both at creating acceptable comfort levels for building users and at potentially achieving energy consumption reduction, leading to energy and cost savings. However, the temperature of a building cannot be arbitrarily set to any value that would imply the least consumption of energy, as it would consequently affect thermal comfort in a significant way. Especially in the case of municipal buildings that are widely used by the public, thermal comfort parameters during operation are defined by technical standards (ASHRAE, 2010).

To this end, this action plan was designed to assist energy managers in adjusting thermal comfort parameters in such a way as to optimize energy use and maintain comfort levels in accepted ranges.

Among others, subjective thermal comfort is calculated using the Predicted Mean Vote (PMV) index [1, 2], a 7-point thermal sensation scale that ranks zero at a neutral thermal feeling and -3, 3 when the user feels cold or hot, respectively. Intermediate values reflect intermediate stages of thermal comfort.

The PMV index can be theoretically calculated by using a number of variables, namely indoor conditions, such as air temperature, mean radiant temperature, relative humidity and relative air velocity and parameters depending on occupants' profiles, such as metabolic rate and clothing level.

2.4.2 Optimization criteria

Changing the temperature set-point inside a building can lead to important energy savings. However, thermal comfort has to remain within accepted levels according to relevant standards (ISO 7730:2005). The philosophy beyond this action plan is to detect the range of accepted temperature inside a building, by finding its correlation to occupants' thermal comfort levels, which is often significantly diverge from predicted ones [3]. In this way, a broader range of accepted set-points is defined and new temperature set-points can be used, towards energy efficiency.

As a result, such an action plan is envisaged to decrease energy consumption, corresponding emissions and relevant energy cost. Consequently, DSS parameters to be optimized are the following:

- Energy consumption
- CO₂ emissions
- Energy cost

2.4.3 Description of the inference rule

Three main values are calculated and examined within this action plan:

PMV (Predicted Mean Vote): This value depends on six variables, namely on Air Temperature, Mean Radiant Temperature, Relative Air Velocity, Relative Humidity, Clothing Insulation, Metabolic Rate and is calculated by the following equations, according to ISO 7730:2005 [1]:

$$PMV = [0,303 \cdot (\exp(-0,036 \cdot M) + 0,028) \cdot (M - W) - 3,05 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot [5,733 - 6,99 \cdot (M - W) - p_a] - 0,42 \cdot [(M - W) - 58,15] - 1,7 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot M \cdot (5,867 - p_a) - 0,0014 \cdot M \cdot (34 - \theta_a) - 3,96 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot f_{cl} \cdot [(\theta_{cl} + 273)^4 - (\bar{\theta}_r + 273)^4] - f_{cl} \cdot h_c \cdot (\theta_{cl} - \theta_a)] \quad (1)$$

$$\theta_{cl} = 35,7 - 0,028 \cdot (M - W) - R_{cl} \cdot \{3,96 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot f_{cl} \cdot [(\theta_{cl} + 273)^4 - (\bar{\theta}_r + 273)^4] + f_{cl} \cdot h_c \cdot (\theta_{cl} - \theta_a)\} \quad (2)$$

$$h_c = \begin{cases} 2,38 \cdot |\theta_{cl} - \theta_a|^{0,25} & \text{for } 2,38 \cdot |\theta_{cl} - \theta_a|^{0,25} > 12,1 \cdot \sqrt{v_a} \\ 12,1 \cdot \sqrt{v_a} & \text{for } 2,38 \cdot |\theta_{cl} - \theta_a|^{0,25} < 12,1 \cdot \sqrt{v_a} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$f_{cl} = \begin{cases} 1,00 + 1,290 \cdot R_{cl} & \text{for } R_{cl} \leq 0,078 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{K/W} \\ 1,05 + 0,645 \cdot R_{cl} & \text{for } R_{cl} > 0,078 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{K/W} \end{cases}, \text{ where:} \quad (4)$$

where:

M is the metabolic rate (W/m²)

W is the effective mechanical power (W/m²)

R_{cl} is the clothing thermal resistance (m²K/W)

f_{cl} is the clothing surface area factor

θ_a is the ambient air temperature (°C)

θ̄_r is the mean radiant temperature (°C)

v_a is the relative air velocity (m/s)

p_a is the water vapour partial pressure (Pa)

h_c is the convective heat transfer coefficient [(W/m²K)]

θ_{cl} is the clothing surface temperature (°C)

Notes: 1 clothing unit = 1 clo = 0.155 m²K/W

1 metabolic unit = 1met = 58,2 W/m²

Within the framework of this action plan, predicted indoor conditions for a week ahead are used in order to calculate the PMV on an hourly basis.

AMV (Actual Mean Vote): This value is not calculated, but is provided to the system via the [Thermal Comfort Validator](#) (TCV), a web application developed within the OPTIMUS framework, accessible by computers or mobile-phones, where building users are encouraged to submit feedback on their thermal sensation (see D2.4). This feedback is then analyzed and evaluated in order to calculate the actual PMV based on users' experiences. The AMV is the direct outcome of the TCV during the days of the week under examination

OMV (Observed Mean Vote): The value of OMV is calculated by the PMV equations, using monitored, and not predicted, values of temperature and humidity, as measured by the building sensors in real-time.

The methodology of the inference rule consists of the following series of steps:

1. **PMV Calculation.** Predicted values of indoor conditions are used in the PMV equation, in order to calculate the Predicted Mean Vote value for a week ahead. Calculations refer to hourly time-slots. The value of air temperature is provided by the “Indoor Temperature Prediction Model”, described in detail in D3.2.
2. **AMV retrieval by TCV Web App.** Building user feedback is registered via the TCV web application and retrieved in real-time per hour. Users contribute by completing a questionnaire, whether they feel cold, cool, slightly cool, neutral, slightly warm, warm or hot. This input is translated into AMV values of -3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2 and 3, respectively.

After collecting individual feedback by the TCV application, a question concerning the exact time when the user felt uncomfortable is arisen. The TCV application captures the time of access by the user, but this does not provide any information on the time interval when the user felt discomfort.

Thus, an assumption that can be made is that the AMV value of the questionnaire refers to the comfort level of the exact time it was completed, expanded before and after by a certain time interval.

This assumption is based on the consideration of the time needed until the user decides to share thermal sensation, as well as the system’s inertia to reflect a change. Therefore, the feedback taken by each questionnaire can be considered to have duration and effect resembling the general scheme presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Generalized feedback duration and effect

As a result, the main feedback is expanded hourly, before and after the exact time of submission, reduced by 0,5 point, until it reaches 0.

3. **AMV Filtering.** The average value of TCV inputs is calculated per hourly time slot. However, further filtering is applied to the AMV values, in order to exclude input provided during non-operating hours of the building. Moreover, the existence of less

than 3 registrations indicates inadequate input and is therefore discarded. After the filtering process, the hourly AMV values are finalized.

4. **OMV Calculation.** During the week under examination, OMV is calculated based on the respective equation and by using monitored temperature and humidity values.
5. **Correlation calculation between AMV-OMV.** A plot is created, with AMV values in the x axis and OMV as y, using the filtered values of AMV and the OMV of the corresponding hourly time slots. The linear expression that best describes their correlation is calculated.
6. **Definition of OMV value that corresponds to AMV=0,** based on the previous equation. In this step the OMV value is defined, while users have a neutral (0) comfort feeling. AMV is set to 0 and the corresponding OMV is calculated.
7. **Definition of the temperature value that corresponds to this OMV.** For the OMV value specified in the previous step, the reverse OMV equation is solved, in order to find the temperature that results to this specific value of OMV, given that the rest of the values are considered equal to the average weekly values.

This temperature value is the main outcome of the action plan: it constitutes a suggestion for the set-point for the following week.

8. **AMV Validation.** In this last step, the results are validated. When the PMV is set equal to OMV, users' actual thermal comfort is supposed to be acceptable. This means that by setting $PMV=OMV$ in the abovementioned linear equation, the AMV should belong to $[-0.5, 0.5]$, in order to comply with ASHRAE Standards (2010)

2.5 Inference Rule 3: Determination of the preferred temperature according to adaptive comfort model

2.5.1 General structure and involved variables

The general structure of the scenario modelling is shown in Figure 7. The following data capturing modules are involved: weather forecasting and social media.

To schedule the set point temperatures, a linear regression is applied according to the predicted outdoor air temperature.

The inference rule process will consist of logical rules that link the predicted indoor set point temperature according to adaptive comfort concept with the output from social media module.

Figure 7. General structure of the action plan

In Table 2 a detailed list of the input variables needed for the modelling process is shown together with their attributes.

Table 2. Listing of the input variables

Input variable		Observed/ predicted	Time aggregation	Spatial scale
Climatic data	Outdoor air temperature	Predicted	Hourly	-

2.5.2 Optimization criteria

According to the adaptive comfort theory and international research investigations, a regression equation aimed at scheduling the indoor set point temperature as a function of the outdoor mean running temperature is proposed. In the adaptive approach the occupant is considered an active subject that interacts with the environment and contributes to determine the conditions of comfort, through repeated feedbacks. Thermal preferences depend on the way the occupants can interact with their environment, changing behavior and adjusting

expectations. Thanks to this fact, some opportunities to save energy for air conditioning can be exploited, considering less restrictive set point temperatures (e.g lower temperature in heating season and higher temperature in cooling season) instead of fixed values.

Consequently, the parameters to be optimized are the following:

- energy consumption
- CO₂ emissions
- thermal comfort

2.5.3 Description of the inference rule

The procedure of this inference rule consists of determining a linear regression of the operative temperature providing indoor comfort as a function of an index of the outdoor air temperature, called *running mean outside temperature*.

The *running mean outside temperature* θ_{rmn} is an exponentially weighted average outdoor temperature, identified as a significantly index correlated with the internal operative temperature of comfort; different studies have shown that this index has a better correlation with the comfort temperatures, compared to others, such as the monthly average outdoor temperature.

Moreover it must be considered that people tend to adapt their clothing, not only to outside weather conditions, but also to the thermal conditions typically expected in indoor environments. This adaptation is higher in case of naturally ventilated environments (partially mechanical control), compared to the case of total mechanically controlled environments. De Dear and Brager show that in naturally ventilated environments temperatures judged as "neutral", depend on both the external and internal climatic conditions. In case of buildings with mechanical climate control (air-conditioned buildings and/or "mixed-mode" conditioning), De Dear and Brager indicate a correlation between the internal operating temperature of neutrality ($\theta_{o,n}$) and average internal operative temperature (θ_o).

Assuming that the mean internal operative temperature is approximately equal to the set point temperature and considering the studies on the relation between θ_{rmn} and comfort neutral temperature, regression curve algorithm for set-point temperatures for environments with mechanical control, as an alternative to a fixed set-point can be identified.

The regression curve which allows to evaluate the set point temperatures as a function of running mean outside temperature (below presented) was found according to adaptive comfort theory and on the basis of a comfort field survey carried out by researchers of Politecnico di Torino.

In the following a description of the model is shown.

1. The predicted hourly outdoor air temperature is recorded for 8 days
2. The daily mean outdoor air temperature is calculated
3. The running mean outside temperature (θ_{rm}) is calculated applying the equation below considering the average daily temperature at n day (with $n = 6$)

$$\theta_{mn} = (1 - c) \cdot [\theta_{dm(n-1)} + c\theta_{dm(n-2)} + c^2\theta_{dm(n-3)} + \dots] \quad (5)$$

Where c is a constant equal to 0,8.

4. The set point temperature is calculated according to equation 5 (6)

$$\text{If } \theta_{mn} < 14^\circ\text{C} \rightarrow \theta_{set,point} = 21,5^\circ\text{C}$$

$$\text{If } 14^\circ\text{C} < \theta_{mn} < 22,5^\circ\text{C} \rightarrow \theta_{set,point} = 0,5861 \cdot \theta_{mn} + 12,531^\circ\text{C} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{If } \theta_{mn} > 22,5^\circ\text{C} \rightarrow \theta_{set,point} = 26^\circ\text{C}$$

2.6 Inference Rule 4: Determination of the optimum start/stop of the heating system

2.6.1 General structure and involved variables

The general structure of the scenario modelling is shown in Figure 8.

Both static and dynamic data are needed. The following data capturing modules are involved: weather forecasting, de-centralized, social media and energy prices. The observed input data from the capturing modules, as well as the forecasted ones from the weather forecasting module, are needed to build the prediction model. The prediction model is based on a grey box approach and it is applied in order to calculate the predicted indoor temperature for a building zone. The inference rule process is a calculation procedure aimed at finding the optimal boost time of the heating system taking into account both thermal comfort and energy prices prediction. It is considered that thermal comfort level is assured through an adaptive comfort approach. Moreover, boost time optimization may also take into account the hourly energy prices fluctuation. According to the energy price prediction, the system can be turned on/off to minimize the energy cost.

Figure 8. General structure of the action plan

According the building partitioning rules as defined in D2.1, the action is related to the zone that can be managed separately from the rest of the building.

In Table 3 a detailed list of the input variables both static and dynamic needed for the modelling process is shown together with their attributes.

Table 3. Listing of the input variable

Input variable		Observed/ predicted	Time aggregation	Spatial scale
Occupancy (occupants)	Occupied/ unoccupied space	Observed/predicted	Hourly	Building zone
On/off heating/cooling system scheduling		Observed	Hourly	Building zone
Space heating/cooling capacity		-	-	Building zone
Climatic data	Outdoor air temperature	Observed/predicted	Hourly	-
Energy generation system	Energy consumption	Observed/predicted	Hourly	Building zone
Thermal comfort	Indoor air temperature	Observed/predicted	Hourly	Building zone

2.6.2 Optimization criteria

During the unoccupied periods, the operation of the heating system is generally reduced according to one of the following modes:

- set back temperature
- cut-off

Before the start of the occupation period, the heating system is generally operated at full power to heat up the building structure and provide comfort conditions to the occupants.

The action plan regards the optimization of the boost time of the heating/cooling system. Specifically, the aim of this specific action is to optimize the boost time taking into account the forecasting of the outdoor air temperature and the occupancy of the building. Moreover, it is considered that the optimal set point temperature is based on the adaptive comfort approach and that the technical system management may be also influenced by the predicted energy price trend.

Therefore, the indicators to be optimized are:

- energy consumption
- CO₂ emissions
- thermal comfort
- energy cost

2.6.3 Description of the inference rule

The main goal of the inference rule is to provide the optimal timing of the switching on of the heating system in order to set the proper set point temperature when the zone is occupied. According to D3.2, the optimal indoor air temperature trend to be obtained is given in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Indoor air temperature trend for cut-off mode (a) and set-back mode (b).

In order to define the trend, the following input data must be known:

- the regressors (τ , Φ/H) as defined in D3.2
- the occupancy profile predicted for the entire week
- the predicted outdoor air temperature coming from the data capturing module.

The following procedure must be followed.

1. The regressors are recorded. The following regressors should be known:
 - time constant of the structure (τ).
 - Φ/H values for boost period.
 - Φ/H values for the cut-off mode.
2. The occupancy profile for the entire week is provided and recorded. For each hour and each zone it must be clear whether the zone is occupied or not.
3. The predicted hourly outdoor air temperature is recorded for the entire week.
4. Once the predicted indoor air temperature of a zone has been calculated according to the procedure described in D3.2, the last day/s of the week before can be considered as the starting point for the week after.
5. To calculate the boost time, in which the heating system is operating with the maximum power, the following equation must be applied

$$\Delta t = \tau \cdot \ln \frac{\theta_{i,0} - \left(\theta_e + \frac{\Phi}{H} \right)}{\theta_{set,point} - \left(\theta_e + \frac{\Phi}{H} \right)} \quad (8)$$

Where the set point temperature ($\theta_{set,point}$) can be defined according to adaptive comfort criteria or to social media rule.

The Φ/H ratios to be used are calculated in D3.2.

To solve equation 1, first test value of $\theta_{i,0}$ and the corresponding θ_e (average outdoor air temperature of the boost period) is defined. A first Δt value is calculated.

The time t_0 at which the heating system is suggested to be switched on is

$$t_0 = t_{\text{set,point}} - \Delta t \quad (9)$$

where $t_{\text{set,point}}$ is the time at which $\theta_{\text{set,point}}$ is reached.

Once t_0 is calculated, the indoor air temperature for the boost period is calculated according to the method described in D3.2.

6. The boost period ends when the indoor air temperature is equal to the set point temperature. The comfort level must be guaranteed for the whole time that the zone is occupied through a normal heating operation. The indoor air temperature trend is considered constant and equal to the set point temperature.
7. The normal heating operation ends when the zone is unoccupied and the heating system is turned off. To calculate the indoor air temperature trend for the cut-off period, the procedure described in D3.2 is applied.
8. The calculation procedure is repeated for each working day

2.7 Inference Rule 5: Assessing free cooling options

2.7.1 General structure and involved variables

The general structure of the modelling scenario is shown in Figure 10. The following data capturing modules are involved: weather forecasting and de-centralized and, secondarily, energy prices. The inference rule consists in the optimization of the management of an air side economizer system varying the proportion of outside air to return air in order to maintain the mixed air temperature set-point. In no case, however, will the outside air fraction be less than the minimum allowed according to suggestions of standard on indoor air quality.

Figure 10. General structure of the action plan

In Table 4 a detailed list of the input variables needed for the modelling process is shown together with their attributes.

Table 4. Listing of the input variable

Input variable		Observed/ predicted	Time aggregation	Spatial scale
Climatic data	Outdoor air temperature Relative humidity	Predicted	Hourly	-
Thermal comfort	Indoor air temperature	Observed	Hourly	Building zone

2.7.2 Optimization criteria

An air-side economizer allows an AHU to use outdoor-air to reduce or eliminate the need for mechanical cooling. When there is a need for cooling and if the outdoor-air conditions are favourable for economizing, unconditioned outdoor-air can be used to meet all of the cooling

energy needs or supplement mechanical cooling. The effect of this strategy is a reduction of energy consumption for cooling energy needs.

In addition free cooling can be exploited with a higher share during night hours when the energy prices are lower. In these hours the shifting of the cooling can be operated as a DSM strategy.

Moreover the air side economizer strategy can be coupled with a demand control ventilation strategy. Ventilation can be reduced during the hours of operation when zones are vacant or occupied lower than the peak occupancy. When ventilation is reduced, the energy can be saved because it is not necessary to heat or cool as much outside air. On the basis of the estimated occupancy the reduction of outdoor air can be managed when the estimated occupancy of spaces served by the system is less than design occupancy.

Scheduled ventilation can work effectively in scheduled meeting rooms. In this system, the occupancy is estimated based on the inference rule 1 and this information is input into the control system. To be effective, the system requires ongoing entry of schedule information or integration with a scheduling calendar system.

The indicators to be optimized are:

- Energy consumption
- CO₂ emissions
- Energy cost

2.7.3 Description of the inference rule

The procedure consists of scheduling the amount of outdoor air to be used for cooling the indoor environment instead of conditioning the return or mixed air, when favourable conditions occur. Air-side economizers HVAC (heating, ventilating, and air conditioning) can save energy by using cool outside air as a mean of cooling the indoor space.

The rule can be based both on the control of the temperature or of the enthalpy of the indoor and outdoor air. When the temperature or enthalpy of the outside air is less than the temperature or enthalpy of the recirculated air, conditioning the outside air is more energy efficient than conditioning recirculated air. When the outside air is both sufficiently cool and sufficiently dry (depending on the climate) no additional conditioning of it is needed (free cooling). Air-side economizers can reduce HVAC energy costs and improving indoor air quality.

This strategy can be coupled with a demand control ventilation in order to optimize the management of the energy consumption related to HVAC system. When an occupancy is estimated to be lower than the design value, a reduction of the outdoor air according to the number of occupants can be set. If conditions favorable to economizer strategy occur during the partial occupancy, a total amount of outdoor air will be supplied in order to exploit all the advantages related to free cooling conditions.

Different strategies can be implemented according to the microclimatic variable (temperature or enthalpy) and to the opportunity to consider a threshold value or the microclimatic condition related to the return air.

Outdoor air temperature: the economizer is enabled whenever the outside air temperature is below a maximum allowed temperature, as specified by user.

Outdoor air enthalpy: the economizer is enabled whenever the outside air enthalpy is below the maximum allowed enthalpy, as specified by the user

Dual temperature: the economizer is enabled whenever the outside air temperature is less than the return air temperature.

Dual enthalpy: the economizer is enabled whenever the outside air enthalpy is less than the return air temperature.

In the following the schematic procedure is presented:

1. The predicted outdoor air temperature together with the indoor air temperature are considered for the entire week. If the rule is based on the control of the enthalpy, also the relative humidity of both indoor and outdoor air must be considered.
2. If the control is based on the temperature, for each hour, the following rules have to be applied:

Outdoor air temperature

If $\theta_{sup} < \theta_e < \theta_{tr}$ → the totally amount of the supply air comes from the outside environment;

If $\theta_{lim} < \theta_e < \theta_{sup}$ → the supply air is partially outdoor air and partially recirculating air;

If $\theta_e \leq \theta_{lim,low}$ → only the minimum amount of outdoor air is needed to be supplied in order to guarantee the indoor environmental quality condition.

Dual temperature

If $\theta_{sup} < \theta_e < \theta_{ret}$ → the totally amount of the supply air comes from the outside environment;

If $\theta_{lim} < \theta_e < \theta_{sup}$ → the supply air is partially outdoor air and partially recirculating air;

If $\theta_e \leq \theta_{lim,low}$ → only the minimum amount of outdoor air is needed to be supplied in order to guarantee the indoor environmental quality condition.

Where

θ_{sup}	is the temperature of the supply air
θ_{tr}	is a threshold temperature value selected by the user
θ_e	is temperature of the outdoor air
θ_{ret}	is the temperature of the recirculating air
$\theta_{lim,low}$	is the outdoor air temperature value that allow to balance the building thermal load with minimum amount of mass flow rate of outdoor air.

The eligible limit value of outdoor air temperature is the following

$$\theta_{\text{lim,low}} = \theta_{\text{des}} - \frac{G_a}{G_e} \cdot (\theta_{\text{des}} - \theta_{\text{sup}}) \quad (10)$$

If the enthalpy is considered as control parameter, the eligible lowest value of the outdoor air enthalpy is the following

$$h_{\text{lim,low}} = h_{\text{des}} - \frac{G_a}{G_e} \cdot (h_{\text{des}} - h_{\text{sup}}) \quad (11)$$

Where

$\theta_{\text{des}}, h_{\text{des}}$ are the design temperature/enthalpy of the indoor air

$\theta_{\text{sup}}, h_{\text{sup}}$ are temperature/enthalpy of the supply air

G_a is the mass flow rate of the supply air

G_e is the mass flow rate of the outdoor air

If the control is based on the enthalpy values, the procedure is the same with enthalpy values (h) instead of temperatures. In Figure 11 the procedure is shown.

Figure 11. General structure of the action plan

2.8 Inference Rule 6: Evaluating the electricity production of the PV system to check possible faults

2.8.1 General structure and involved variables

Electricity produced by PV can significantly contribute towards cost effective energy management. Therefore, ensuring the effective operation of a plant through frequent maintenance is essential in order to avoid efficiency decrease that may result to limited energy production, decreased incomes and deviations from CO₂ emissions targets.

To this end, the current action plan aims at the detection of the need for maintenance and communicate with an alert the user prompting for appropriate maintenance actions.

Electricity produced by PV depends on a number of variables, mainly weather conditions (solar radiation, temperature, humidity, cloud coverage), age and operational condition of the equipment, as well as the exact time of the day (hour, month).

When comparing the real-time monitored values of production with the forecasted values, detection of deviations is possible. The main assumption made in this action plan is that any significant deviation between actual and predicted values is caused by external variables that have not been considered by the model and may constitute possible reasons to check the system for maintenance.

In the above way, abnormalities and identification of possible problems can be facilitated.

2.8.2 Optimization criteria

By identifying operational abnormalities and properly maintaining the PV system, it is envisaged that decrease in the PV production will be prevented and reversed. Increased PV production also improves the energy mix used by the municipal building, leading to a respective decrease in CO₂ emissions. Consequently, the parameters to be optimized are the following:

- Energy consumption
- Renewable energy production
- CO₂ emissions

2.8.3 Description of the inference rule

The methodology of this inference rule can be summarized in the following four steps:

1. **Generation of PV production forecasts based on a robust MLR model.**

The first step of the presented methodology is to obtain reliable forecasts for the energy produced by the PV plants of the examined pilot building. Details regarding the development

of the models can be found in Deliverable 3.2. In brief, a Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) Model is used to forecast energy production for each hour of the day. In this respect we manage to accurately represent how the independent variables – *weather data* - (x_i) linearly connect with the dependent variable – *energy production* - (y_i), according to the following formulas:

$$\text{Observed Data: } y = b_0 + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + \dots + b_px_p + \varepsilon \quad (12)$$

$$\text{Predicted Data: } y' = b_0 + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + \dots + b_px_p \quad (13)$$

$$\text{Error: } \varepsilon = y - y' \quad (14)$$

The individual hourly forecasts are then sorted by date in order to obtain the corresponding forecasts for the upcoming week. At this point it is noted that the error of the model can be caused either by the misspecification of the coefficients of the models (a_i and b_i) or by the influential effect of additional variables that were not considered, such as dirt on the panels' surface, poor maintenance etc.

2. Specification of prediction interval

Although the point forecasts provided by the developed model are assumed to be accurate, there will always be a deviation between the actual and the predicted values. Thus, apart from the point forecasts, the model also provides a prediction interval with a probability of 95%. This will be the estimated interval in which, given a probability of 95%, the future observations will fall based on available data. A depiction of the models prediction intervals, with relation to the production levels, for the case of the Sant Cugat, is presented in Figure 12.

Figure 12. PV production and prediction interval. In cases where the actual production (blue line) is beyond the prediction intervals (green and purple line) a maintenance action should possibly be considered.

The main concept behind this inference rule is that for any observation outside the prediction intervals, a variable not included in the MLR model will be responsible. Such a variable could be, among others, a potential damage of equipment, a failure of the monitoring system or dirt on the panels' surface.

3. Deviation check of predicted and actual values

As the particular model was designed to provide a 95% accuracy, when a deviation between predicted and actual values is detected and exceeds the 5% accepted error, an alarm should be sent by the system, in order to notify the user of the possible need for maintenance of the PV system. More specifically, the system checks for cases like the ones described earlier on hourly basis and creates a table of "Hourly Alarms" with values of 1 and 0 for values exceeding the prediction intervals or not, respectively. Figure 13 illustrates a case in which the observed value of production fell outside the prediction interval, as it presented a deviation of more than 5% of the predicted value. Such a case would set an alarm by the system.

Figure 13: Alarm triggered by an observed value outside the prediction interval

4. Calculation of risk scores

Undoubtedly, not every single alarm is an indication of maintenance. For example, an unexpected cloudy day will lead to poor energy production and possibly to many hourly alarms, although this phenomenon is unrelated with the maintenance of the PV plant. Also, sporadic alarms of insignificant importance might occur from day to day leading to confusing results. In this respect, apart from the hourly alarms, the alarms of each day and week are also calculated by aggregating hourly energy production on daily and weekly frequencies. Then, each day obtains a risk score based on the alarms detected the corresponding day and seven days before that. The risk score is then normalized and in such a way becomes free from temporal failures of the models.

5. Evaluation of total risk scores and creation of alerts

As described in step 4, days with non-systematic alarms, such as sparse alarms with duration of only an hour, will get a low risk score, as they may be of random nature. Respectively, the longer the time interval in which the alarms exist –here we check alarms within a duration of a week-, the higher the final risk score will be. To answer which risk scores are significant and indicate possible failure of the system, we represent the distribution of the alarms and detect the top 90% of the available sample. Any day within this sample is considered of high risk and an alert is sent to the system to warn the user of the DSS.

As an example, in Figure 14 the alerts (red dots) created by the system are presented for a sample of 210 days for the case of the Sant Cugat pilot. As it is shown, given the original data, there seems to be only a systematic problem between the 50th and the 60th day of the sample. Let us now consider that the actual energy production was 20% lower during the first month (30 days) of the sample due to poor maintenance. As shown in Figure 15, the system has successfully detected low performance of the plant and sent alerts to the user.

Figure 14. Alerts (red dots) created by the system given a random sample of 210 days for the Sant Cugat pilot – Original Data.

Figure 15. Alerts (red dots) created by the system given a random sample of 210 days for the Sant Cugat pilot – The original energy production was decreased manually by 20% for the first 30 days of the sample.

2.9 Inference Rule 7: Shifting electrical loads to optimize PV performance

The action related to this inference rule concerns with the optimization (for the next days) of selling/self-using of electricity produced by a photovoltaic system considering different scenarios of energy market. During the hours of electricity production by photovoltaic system the energy market can provide different sell/purchase energy prices for energy management of buildings. Considering the market energy prices it can be observed that photovoltaic systems in public buildings generally help to reduce the energy demand during times of high tariffs. In addition in office public buildings some DSM (Demand Side Management) potentials could be exploited because some opportunities (suggested in technical literature) to shift the electrical load can be implemented.

Some devices with DSM potential (either with internal storage mechanism or chronologically non-critical operation) can be used whenever possible. For example workplaces are equipped with laptops, which can switch to battery operation during times of high electricity prices.

Other opportunities regarding DSM potential are related to heating or cooling processes of the building. During the heating period, the building can be preheated to a higher temperature level outside the operation time, which leads to a lower power consumption during the high-tariff period in the daytime. During the cooling period, the procedure works conversely, so that, during the night, the building is chilled down to reduce the consumption during the day. Another opportunity which will be considered in the inference rule 7 is related to the air side economizer system. In fact due to lower temperatures during the night, it is very likely that the shifting of the cooling to the night hours leads to a higher share of free cooling.

In general the potential to apply DSM actions needs to be carefully coupled with the management of PV system energy production in order to obtain the maximum exploitation of solar energy. Otherwise, the on-site usage of energy produced by PV could be lowered due to the utilization of DSM potential. This situation can be avoided by the selective use of electricity by consumers with load shift potential during daytime in order to maximize the self-using of renewable energy during the hours when it is convenient from economic point of view.

Moreover it can be observed that some electrical loads need to be shifted during the day, while some opportunities to shift electrical loads from a day to another day during the week can be explored. Considering that the DSS provide a schedule for the next week on sale/consumption management of the electricity produced by PV system, DSM strategies weekly based could be implemented.

On the basis of the above reasoning different scenarios are introduced. They are categorized according to three different strategies:

- green strategy
- finance strategy
- peak strategy

2.9.1 General structure and involved variables

The input data for the development of the inference rule and reported in in Table 5, coming from the data mining process as described in D3.2

Table 5. Listing of the input variable

Input variable	Observed/ predicted	Time aggregation	Spatial scale
Weather Forecasting	Observed/predicted	Hourly	
Energy Demand Load Profile	Predicted	Hourly	Building zone
Estimated Energy Generation Load Profile	Predicted	Hourly	Building zone
Hourly estimated energy sell price	Predicted	Hourly	-
Hourly estimated energy purchase cost	Predicted	Hourly	-

In Figure 16 an example of a daily electrical energy demand profile and energy generation profile by PV is shown.

Figure 16. Profile of energy demand and energy produced by PV

In particular the variables which need to be taken into account are:

- the purchase cost of electricity from the grid [€/kWh]
- the selling prices of electricity produced by photovoltaic system [€/kWh]
- hourly electricity demand [kWh]
- hourly electricity production by renewable sources [kWh].

2.9.2 Optimization criteria

Electricity produced by PV can significantly contribute towards a cost effective energy management. The proposed optimization procedure can contribute on one side to improve the exploitation of solar energy maximizing the self-consumption of electricity produced on-site, and on the other side to take advantage from the selling of the surplus of energy produced considering the energy market. The photovoltaic systems can effectively help to reduce the energy consumption and consequently CO₂ emission and in particular during times of high energy tariffs. In addition some DSM potentials consisting in the shifting of some electrical loads can be considered and coupled in the optimization criteria. This coupling is useful to assure that demand does not fall below PV-production when it is convenient to use the energy (maximize the self-using of PV energy) or to create surplus of energy (by means of load shifting strategies) when it is convenient to sell the energy produced through the PV system.

The indicators to be optimized are:

- Energy consumption
- Renewable energy production
- CO₂ emissions
- Income from the sale of surplus of energy produced through PV system

2.9.3 Description of the inference rule

In the following a synthetic description (based on steps) of each strategy is presented. In the next section a detailed description for each strategy is carried out.

Green Strategy

- if $E_{gen} > E_{dem}$ and $S_{price} > P_{cost}$ then then sell the surplus of energy;
- if $E_{gen} > E_{dem}$ and $S_{price} \leq P_{cost}$ then try to shift electrical loads in these hours;
- If $E_{gen} < E_{dem}$ then use the energy from PV.

Finance Strategy

- If $(E_{gen} - E_{dem})^+$ exists and $S_{price} > P_{cost}$ than sell the surplus of energy;
- If $(E_{gen} - E_{dem})^+$ exists and $S_{price} \leq P_{cost}$ then try to shift electrical loads in these hours (the electrical loads should be shifted from hours with $S_{price} > P_{cost}$ and $(E_{dem} - E_{gen})^+ < X\%E_{dem}$;

Peak Strategy

- If $(E_{dem} - E_{gen}) > E^*$ shift electric loads in surplus hours with a negative price check if they exist in order to cover the energy surplus.

- If extra demand after load shifting continues to exist then shift the residual extra demand in hours with the lowest purchase cost of energy (in X% of the cases) in the whole day considering their maximum capacity ($E^* - (E_{\text{dem}} - E_{\text{gen}})^+$).

2.9.3.1 Green strategy

The green strategy is based on the opportunity to manage the energy produced by PV in such a way to maximize the self-using of PV energy considering the market energy prices.

When using photovoltaic production, it should be considered that, for surplus feed in tariffs, it is normally more economic to use the electricity on-site than to provide it to the network operator.

In the green strategy is included a *price check* during the hours when a surplus of energy produced by PV occurs. The price check is positive when the selling price of energy produced by PV is higher than the purchase cost of energy from the grid. In this case the affordability of selling energy is verified and this action is suggested by the inference rule. If the price check is negative during the hours when a surplus of energy occurs, the cost savings consequent to use of energy overcomes the potential income consequent to sell this surplus of energy. For this reason in this case the inference rule suggests an electrical loads shifting during these hours (exploiting the potential of DSM) in order to maximize the self-using of energy. The impact of load shifting measures on the share of on-site used electricity produced by PV can be remarkable.

This strategy indeed tends to maximize the daily amount of energy from renewable sources self-used without considering the opportunity to take advantage from the selling of energy produced by PV during the hours when a surplus of energy produced does not occurs. The selling of energy is expected only during the hours when a surplus of energy generated by PV over demand occurs and when the market prices are favourable.

This strategy therefore, include actions aimed at selling energy produced by PV exclusively during the hours when a surplus of energy produced by PV occurs.

In Figure 17 an example of an energy demand and energy generation profiles, as well as the energy produced by PV and self-used by the building, is shown. In the figure the potential of surplus of energy produced by PV is also indicated.

Figure 17. Energy profile generated through the application of the green strategy

The rule at the base of green strategy is in the following presented:

For each hour:

- if $E_{gen} > E_{dem}$ and price check is positive then sell the surplus of energy
- if $E_{gen} > E_{dem}$ and price check is negative then try to shift electrical loads during these hours;
- If $E_{gen} < E_{dem}$ then use the energy from PV

2.9.3.1.1 Schematic procedure

The implemented inference rule follows this procedure:

1. for each hour calculate the amount of surplus energy $E_{surplus} = (E_{gen} - E_{dem})^+$ if it exist;
2. during the hours in which surplus occurs do a price check;
3. during the hours when the price check is verified (positive) sell the surplus of energy
4. during the hours when the price check is not verified (negative) try to shift electrical loads in these hours in order to maximize the self-using of renewable energy;
5. in the new configuration (after the application of the strategy) calculate the net income if the surplus exist

$$Net\ income\ [€] = (E_{gen} - E_{dem})^+ [kWh] * Energy\ sale\ price\ [€/kWh] \quad (15)$$

6. for each day calculate the total cost saving deriving from the energy produced by PV and self-used

$$cost\ saving\ [€] = (E_{gen} - (E_{gen} - E_{dem})^+) \left[\frac{€}{kWh} \right] * Energy\ Purchase\ cost \left[\frac{€}{kWh} \right] \quad (16)$$

7. for each day sum the net income and the cost saving.

The daily amount of energy produced by PF and self-used in the building represents a useful metric to measure the impact of this strategy.

2.9.3.2 Finance strategy

In the finance strategy during the hours when the energy produced by the photovoltaic system does not exceed the energy demand, but the price check is positive, the rule suggests to create a surplus. The surplus of energy generated by PV over the energy demand is created through DSM strategies shifting the electrical loads. As a consequence the rule suggests to sell this surplus of energy in order to increase the daily income.

For each hour a preliminary check of prices is performed. During the hours when a surplus of energy exist and the price check is positive the rule suggests to sell the energy similarly to green strategy.

Instead, during the hours when a surplus of energy occurs and the price check is negative the rule makes it possible to individuate the hours in which the price check is positive and it is possible to create a surplus through energy savings opportunities or through a load shifting management. Moreover, in the load shifting case the rule suggests to shift the electrical loads in the hours when a surplus of energy with a negative price check is verified in order to promote the self-using of energy by PV.

The rule at the base of this approach is in the following presented:

- If $(E_{gen} - E_{dem})^+$ exists and the price check is positive then sell the surplus of energy;
- If $(E_{gen} - E_{dem})^+$ exists and the price check is negative then try to shift electrical loads in these hours (the electrical loads should be shifted from hours with a positive price check and $(E_{dem} - E_{gen})^+ < X\%E_{dem}$);

2.9.3.2.1 Schematic procedure

1. for each hour do a price check
2. if $(E_{gen} - E_{dem})^+$ exists and the price check is positive than sell the surplus of energy;
3. if $(E_{gen} - E_{dem})^+$ exists and the price check is negative then try to shift electrical load in these hours from the hours where the price check is positive and it is possible to create a surplus of energy;
4. the hours where the opportunity to create a surplus exists are identified. They are characterized by these properties: the price check is positive and $(E_{dem} - E_{gen})^+ < X\%E_{dem}$, and it is possible to shift an amount of energy higher than $X\%E_{dem}$;
5. in the new configuration after the application of the strategy calculate the net income if the surplus exist;

$$Net\ income\ [€] = (E_{gen} - E_{dem})^+ [kWh] * Energy\ sale\ price\ [€/kWh] \quad (17)$$

6. for each day calculate the total cost saving deriving from energy produced by PV and self-used;

$$cost\ saving\ [€] = (E_{gen} - (E_{gen} - E_{dem})^+) \left[\frac{€}{kWh} \right] * Energy\ Purchase\ cost \left[\frac{€}{kWh} \right] \quad (18)$$

7. for each day sum the net incomes and the cost saving

The total income consequent to the selling of energy produced by PV represents a useful metric to measure the impact of this strategy.

2.9.3.3 Peak strategy

The peak strategy is based on the opportunity to not overcome a defined threshold of net average power demand E^* set in advance by the user. E^* is defined as the highest hourly value of net average power demand for the X% of cases in a whole day (e.g. from 70th percentile to 95th percentile). For example selecting the 95th percentile means that the threshold is the highest value except for the 5% of the cases in the whole day.

This strategy could be the most suitable in order to maximize the load factor. The increasing of Load factor ($LF = \frac{\sum \text{hourly energy demand}}{\text{Daily maximum hourly Paverage} \cdot 24 \text{ hours}}$) ensure peaks shaving and network stability.

The goal of this strategy is to apply demand side management strategies to encourage the consumer to use less energy during peak hours or to move the time of energy use to off-peak times.

In the peak strategy, it is possible to select the most appropriate hours in which it is convenient to shift extra demand without risk of decreasing the load factor or creating new peaks considering also the minimization of the costs.

The most suitable hours in which it is convenient to shift the extra net average power demand depends on the surplus of energy produced by PV (with negative price check) and on the capacity to receive shifted energy of the no peak hours with low energy purchase cost. In particular the hours in which it is convenient to shift the extra net average power demand are selected with the following priority:

1. Working hours in which there is a surplus of energy produced with a negative price check,
2. Working hours in which $(E^* - (E_{dem} - E_{gen})^+) > 0$ with the lowest purchase cost of energy for X% of the cases in the whole day.

The rules at the base of this approach is in the following presented:

- If $(E_{dem} - E_{gen}) > E^*$ shift electric loads in surplus hours with a negative price check if they exist in order to cover the energy surplus.
- If extra demand after load shifting continues to exist then shift the residual extra demand in hours with the lowest purchase cost of energy (in X% of the cases) in the whole day considering their maximum capacity $(E^* - (E_{dem} - E_{gen})^+)$.

Schematic procedure

1. for each hour do a price check
2. for each hour evaluate the net average power demand $(E_{dem} - E_{gen})^+$
3. evaluate the threshold E^* . In particular the threshold can be decided by the user selecting the percentile (from 70th percentile to 95th percentile) of $(E_{dem} - E_{gen})^+$ daily distribution;
4. if surplus hours with positive price check exists then sell the surplus of energy;
5. if surplus hours with negative price check exist execute step 6, else execute step 8;
6. for each hour If maximum net average power demand is higher than E^* then shift extra demand $((E_{dem} - E_{gen})^+ - E^*)^+$ in surplus hours with a negative price check until covering the surplus of energy.
7. if the extra demand after the step 6 continues to exist then execute step 8, else execute step 9;
8. shift the extra demand in hours with the lowest purchase cost of energy (in X% of the cases) in the whole day considering their maximum capacity $(E^* - (E_{dem} - E_{gen})^+)$.
9. in the new configuration after the application of the strategy calculate the net income if the surplus exist;

$$Net\ income\ [€] = (E_{gen} - E_{dem})^+ [kWh] * Energy\ sale\ price\ [€/kWh] \quad (19)$$

10. for the day calculate the total cost saving deriving from the use of energy

$$cost\ saving\ [€] = (E_{gen} - (E_{gen} - E_{dem})^+) \left[\frac{€}{kWh} \right] * Energy\ Purchase\ cost \left[\frac{€}{kWh} \right] \quad (20)$$

11. for the day sum the net incomes and the cost saving
12. in the new configuration calculate the load factor of the $(E_{dem} - E_{gen})^+$ profile.

The load factor is the most suitable metric to measure the impact of this strategy. The metric measure the peak shaving effect consequent to the application of inference rule.

2.9.4 Nomenclature

Table 6.. Nomenclature

Symbol	Units	Description
E_{dem}	kWh	energy demand
E_{gen}	kWh	energy generation from PV
S_{price}	€/kWh	Sell price of energy
P_{cost}	€/kWh	Purchase cost of energy
E^*	kWh	Threshold of net average power demand
LF	-	Load factor

2.10 Inference Rule 8: Determination of the energy source to cover the demand, considering battery charging, RES production and the grid

2.10.1 General structure and involved variables

The general structure of the modelling scenario is shown in Figure 18. The following data capturing modules are involved: weather forecasting and de-centralized. This inference rule determines the energy source to be used to cover electricity demand, according to predefined prioritization. Energy sources to be considered include the system's battery (storage), PV production (or other renewable energy sources, e.g. CHP) and the grid. In case of surplus of energy production and inexistence of peaks, the inference rule determines the energy flow to the battery and its selling to the grid. In the rest of the cases, battery will be charged and discharged accordingly in order to minimize the energy cost based on the forecasted energy price. In this respect, the action plan based on this rule will use the outcome of the energy demand and RES prediction models as well as weather and energy prices forecasts as an input to simulate the energy flows from/to the grid and the batteries to estimate the energy cost of the buildings for the upcoming week.

Figure 18. General structure of the inference rule

In Table 7 a detailed list of the input variables needed for the modelling process is shown together with their attributes.

Table 7: Listing of the input variable

Input variable		Observed/ predicted	Time aggregation	Spatial scale
Climatic data	Outdoor air temperature/ Humidity/Pressure/ Wind Direction/Solar radiation/Dew point/Wind Speed	Observed/ Predicted	Hourly	-
Energy data	Energy consumption/Energy production	Observed/ Predicted	Hourly	Building zone
Other static data	Battery capacity/Minimum charge of battery	-	-	Building zone

2.10.2 Optimization criteria

This inference rule will allow buildings with hybrid systems like the one displayed below (including both energy production systems and storage mechanisms) to optimize the energy flow from/to the batteries and their selling/buying strategy to/from the grid. This is expected to reduce the energy bought from the grid, increase the income of the building and potentially minimize its CO₂ emissions.

Figure 19. Electrical network of PV, storage, CHP and grid

2.10.3 Impact of the inference rule to SCEAF indicators

In the following tables an analysis of the SCEAF indicators optimized through the specific action plan is presented.

1st Pillar: Political Field of Action

Indicator	Description	Result
1.4	Medium term results for CO ₂ reduction in Municipal Buildings	Decrease of CO ₂ emissions

1.5	Medium term results for renewable energy sources in the final use in Municipal Buildings	Increase energy used from RES
-----	--	-------------------------------

2nd Pillar: Energy and Environmental Profile

Indicator	Description	Result
2.3	Average CO ₂ emission factor	The total energy consumption is decreased (denominator), as well as the proportion of each energy carrier in the mix.

3rd Pillar: Related Infrastructures and ICT

Indicator	Description	Result
3.3	Forecasting systems	Additional forecasting system used within the building
3.5	Cost reduction for energy needs (gas, petroleum and electricity) in the municipal building	Decrease of energy consumption, leads to the avoidance of costs of fuel purchase

2.10.4 Description of the inference rule

The inference rule takes into consideration, on an hourly basis, the energy produced and the energy consumed from the building and suggests based on the forecasted energy prices and the peaks which action should be applied in order to take full advantage of its own energy sources and minimize the energy bought from the grid. This could also lead to increased income and reduced CO₂ emissions, if at some point the RES production surplus the energy demand. At this point we note that, although the optimization process is applied on the hourly energy data of the upcoming week, heuristics take into consideration the monthly charging formula of the energy provider since, regardless the optimization of the energy flows on daily basis, peak penalties are calculated based on the maximum energy demand of each month.

In order to do so, the inference rule gives full priority to the charging of the batteries, meaning that if RES production is greater than the demand, the batteries will be charged to their maximum capacity (if possible) and the rest of the energy will be sold to the grid. In the opposite scenario, the batteries will be discharged to their minimum accepted level (if possible) and the surplus energy needed will be bought from the grid. Undoubtedly, energy prices of each charging zone and peaks can modify the original suggestions accordingly. This set of rules is cited below:

Peak shaving heuristics: *These are applied before the Energy prices heuristics to shave peaks and are independent of any further optimization considering energy prices.*

Does the forecasted peak demand across the examined day minus the PV production at this point exceed the maximum hourly energy demand of the month?

- Yes: Calculate the amount of energy needed to make it lower and the energy produced till this time
 - Is past PV production greater than the energy needed?
 - Yes: Charge batteries accordingly at the beginning of the day (till the maximum if needed) and discharge them during the detected peak
 - No: Charge batteries from the beginning of the day and discharge them during the detected peak
- No: Proceed with optimization based on the energy prices of the individual charging zones

Energy prices heuristics: *These are applied in order to further minimize energy cost, based on the energy price of each charging zone.*

Is there a more expensive charging zone till the end of day?

- Yes: Is the state of the battery the maximum?
 - Yes: Is PV production greater than Energy Demand?
 - Yes: Cover energy demand through PV production. Sell the surplus (if any) to the grid.
 - No: Cover (if any available) part of energy demand with PV production Buy the rest from the grid.
 - No: Charge the batteries (if PV production is available). Cover energy demand or part of it through the rest of PV production (if any). In case of surplus sell to the grid. Otherwise buy from it to cover the remaining demand.
- No: Is PV Production greater or equal with the Energy Demand?
 - Yes: Cover Energy Demand through PV Production. Is there a surplus?
 - Yes: Is the state of the battery the maximum?
 - Yes: Sell the surplus to the grid.
 - No: Charge the batteries. If there is still a surplus, sell it to the grid.
 - No: Proceed by optimizing the next hour
 - No: Cover (if any available) part of energy demand with PV production. Is the state of the battery the minimum?
 - Yes: Buy the rest energy needed from the main grid
 - No: Discharge the battery till the minimum (if needed). - Buy the rest from the grid.

Undoubtedly, the effect of the present inference rule is closely related to the capacity of the batteries and the level of RES production compared to the electricity demand of the building. For example, in Figure 20, the inference rule is applied on a random interval of 90 continuous observations of the Savona Campus energy dataset. The black line represents the energy demand of the building, the red line the energy bought from the grid, the green line the PV production and the blue line the storage of the system. As seen, due to the low capacity of the batteries and the small power of the PV plant, no significant changes can be detected. However, supposed that the power of the plant was five times bigger, a lot of advantages arise, as displayed in Figure 21.

Figure 20. Random data from the Savona Campus: Original PV production

Figure 21. Random data from the Savona Campus: Assume 5 time larger PV production

In order to implement the inference rule to the DSS, all of the input variables presented in Figure 18 have to be individually forecasted. This includes forecasting the weather data highlighted in Table 7, the PV and CHP production of the building, as well as its total electricity demand. Then, the rest of the variables, that is electricity being stored/absorbed to/from the batteries and energy bought/sold from/to the grid are estimated using the inference rule. The training of the forecasting models is based on the historical data of the building that are being monitored and collected from the DSS.

2.11 Inference Rule 9: Peak shaving towards energy cost optimization

The action related to this inference rule concerns the minimization of the energy cost of a building given that (*optionally*) different charging zones exist within its operational hours and that (*mandatorily*) an adequate percentage of the building's total load can be redistributed within each day. The inference rule detects cost shaving opportunities based on the charging policy of the electricity supplier and the predicted energy demand and prices of the upcoming week. The output of the rule is a schedule for redistributing loads so that the adjusted demand sums up to the predicted one but leads to a more economical solution, mainly due to reduced (shaved) peaks.

2.11.1 General structure and involved variables

The general structure of the modelling scenario is shown in Figure 22. The following data capturing modules are involved: weather forecasting, de-centralized and energy prices. Weather data are used to forecast energy load, while energy prices in order to determine which charging zones are expected to be cheaper during the examined period. De-centralized data are used to specify and predict energy demand or additional energy flows of the building.

More specifically, in a generic scenario the inference rule may be applied in a building with various energy flows coming from RES, storage and the main grid. The energy of these flows may be significant and should definitely be taken into consideration. In this respect, given a RES production and the rules the system uses to cover its energy needs, predicting PV or CHP production and the energy stored to the batteries of the system may also be needed. In that case relative de-centralized data should be provided in order to define, based on the total load, the energy required or even sold to the main grid. In the most simplified scenario (no energy production and storage), the forecasted load would be the same with the energy bought from the energy supplier.

Concerning energy prices, the data required by the inference rule are closely related with the examined building and the charging policy of the electricity supplier. In a generic scenario energy prices may be changed every month or even within the day. This would require forecasting energy prices systematically in order to detect cost saving opportunities and relative historical data should be mined. In a more simplified scenario, energy prices might be known (static energy prices or announced for a specific period) and no prediction models or historical data would be needed.

Figure 22. General structure of the inference rule

In Table 8 a detailed list of the input variables needed for the modelling process is shown together with their attributes.

Table 8: Listing of the input variable

Input variable		Observed/ predicted	Time aggregation	Spatial scale
Climatic data	Outdoor air temperature/ Humidity/Pressure/ Wind Direction/Solar radiation/Dew point/Wind Speed	Observed/ Predicted	Hourly	-
Energy prices	Historical data or announced prices	Observed/ Predicted	Hourly	-
Energy data	Energy consumption/Energy production	Observed/ Predicted	Hourly	Building zone
Other static data	Battery capacity/Minimum charge of battery	-	-	Building zone

2.11.2 Optimization criteria

This inference rule will allow buildings to minimize energy cost based on the charging policy of their suppliers, the energy prices (actual or predicted), the predicted energy demand and the rest (if any) of the predicted energy flows of the system. Given that the load is just redistributed so that lower peaks are achieved and that the total energy demand remains the same after the implementation of the inference rule, energy savings cannot be achieved by

reducing the total energy demand from the grid. In this respect, energy shaving opportunities arise in two different directions: Moving loads between different charging zones and peak shaving.

In case a penalty is applied to the maximum energy consumption of the day or the month, peaks should be first shaved to reduce it. Loads from the peaks will be removed from the peak hour and will be placed before and after it. In a different case, loads will just be moved from the most expensive to the least expensive charging zone.

At this point we note that the inference rule can be applied only to the shiftable load of the building, as defined by the corresponding energy manager, and changes are considered only between its operational hours. Moreover, given that re-scheduling meetings or working timetables is easier to be applied within the same day of arrangements, the rule is further limited within the day examined.

2.11.3 Description of the inference rule

The inference rule takes into consideration, on an hourly basis, the energy requested by the grid, as calculated after the forecasted energy load, RES production and energy storage has been taken into account (if any). The actions applied are closely related with the energy price of each hour and the existence of peak loads. More specifically, the methodology followed is summarized in the next steps:

- **Stage 1:** *Energy prices are predicted using an appropriate forecasting model.*
 - Based on the available data set, the absolute energy price of each charging zone or its differences can be forecasted to indicate which will be the least expensive.
 - In case the energy prices are static or announced for the examined period, no forecasting is required and the charging zones are automatically sorted based on their absolute values.
- **Stage 2:** *Prediction of energy flows*
 - The hourly energy load of the building is predicted using an appropriate forecasting model.
 - In case of RES production, energy produced by the system is also forecasted for the same period
 - Taking into consideration the rules applied to cover the energy demand of the building (energy flows between the main grid, the RES, the building and the batteries) the energy requested by the main grid is calculated.
- **Stage 3:** *Identification of peak shaving opportunities*
Based on the suggestions of the energy manager, the load which can be moved from one to another hour of the day is detected per day. As a usual case, a percentage of the total load is assumed to be shiftable (from 25% to 5%) and calculated based on the maximum consumption during the day. The minimization of this peak is the main objective of the inference rule.

- **Stage 4: Implementation of the rules**

At this stage the rules for redistributing load from one hour to another are applied. The rules can be summarized as follows:

Static rules:

1. No more than the shiftable load can be redistributed during the day
2. The load can be redistributed only within the operational hours of the day
3. No load can be moved to or from another day

Dynamic rules:

1. If the peak of the day is higher than the last recorded within the charging period, reduce it so that they are equal. In case the load which can be moved is less than the energy required to do so, remove only the available amount of energy.
2. Start moving energy from the cheapest to the most expensive charging zones.
3. If the added energy leads to a peak higher than the last recorded within the charging period, move it to the next preferable hour and stop load shifting when the process is completed or no preferable hours are available.
4. In case no differences are detected between the available hours, equally redistribute the available amount of energy so that lower peaks become available.
5. If no peaks are detected, redistribute energy load using the rules of steps 2 to 4.
6. If no peaks are detected and no cheaper hours are available no action needs to be made.

- **Stage 5: Calculation of the total changes made for the examined period and exportation.**

The redistributed energy load is subtracted from the original one in order to highlight the changes need to be made. These are summarized and exported in order to be used by the energy manager and plan relative actions.

For example, in Figure 23, the inference rule is applied on a random week of the Savona Campus energy dataset. The black line represents the energy demand of the building, the red line the energy bought from the grid, the green line the PV production and the blue line the storage of the system. As seen in the plot above, which displays the energy flows after the implementation of the rule, energy demand from grid has lower peaks during the days compared with the original data (plot below) leading to a more flatted load. The suggestions (add or remove load) are given for a day at the table on the left.

Month	Day	Hour	Load Shift
2	10	0	0
2	10	1	0
2	10	2	0
2	10	3	0
2	10	4	0
2	10	5	0
2	10	6	0
2	10	7	-80,25
2	10	8	5,2
2	10	9	50,85
2	10	10	130,55
2	10	11	71,1
2	10	12	1,45
2	10	13	0
2	10	14	0
2	10	15	11,85
2	10	16	12,15
2	10	17	9,05
2	10	18	32,85
2	10	19	-117,5
2	10	20	-127,3
2	10	21	0
2	10	22	0
2	10	23	0
2	11	0	0
2	11	1	0

Figure 23. Implementation of the rule on the Savona Campus data

At this point we note that in order to implement the rule in the Savona Campus, inference rule 8 “Determination of the energy source to cover the demand, considering battery charging, PV production and the grid” had to been applied on the load and PV production forecasts.

3 Application of the Inference Rules: Action Plans

3.1 Action Plan 1: Scheduling and management of the occupancy

This Action Plan is based on the implementation of Inference Rule 1: Rationalizing the displacement of the occupants.

In the following, an example of application of the procedure is given.

3.1.1 Description of data and building partitioning

In Figure 24 the building partitioning is presented for the Zaanstad Town Hall. The rule is applied to the office part of the building, named zone GH, EF, CD.

Figure 24. General structure of the inference rule

The white model approach described in section 2.3 was applied to three building zones of Zaanstad Town Hall as shown in Figure 24.

In Table 9 the principal geometrical characteristics of the zones are reported.

Table 9. Geometrical characteristics of the three zones of the Zaanstad Town Hall

Zone	V_n	A_f
	m^3	m^2
GH	72.900	3.645
EF	75.700	3.785
CD	78.900	3.945

Where V_n is the net volume and A_f is the net floor area.

The simplified energy model was applied to each zone considering the IWEC weather dataset¹ of Amsterdam. The thermal envelope building properties as well as the geometry data were obtained from the energy performance certification and the site inspection of the technical systems. A standard use of the building (e.g. internal heat gains, management of the shading devices, heating and cooling season modes etc.) is considered.

The results of the energy model are shown in Figures 25 and 26. Figure 25 reports the global heat loss coefficient (H), while Figure 26 presents the energy need for space heating ($Q_{H,nd}$). As regards the cooling period, according to the procedure above described, no energy need ($Q_{C,nd}$) is required.

Figure 25. Heat loss coefficient for the three zones of Zaanstad Town Hall

Figure 26. Energy need for space heating for the three zones of Zaanstad Town Hall

In this example, as shown in the above Figures, there aren't significant differences among zones in term of energy need for space heating since the zones are characterized by similar compactness factor, thermal envelope characteristics as well as main orientation. However, the output of the analysis suggests to give priority to zone GH.

¹ https://energyplus.net/weather-location/europe_wmo_region_6/NLD//NLD_Amsterdam.062400_IWEC

For each zone, the elaboration procedure of the estimation of the occupancy is developed according to section 2.1 to estimate the number of people present for a standard week. In the following section the estimation model is shown together with the inference rule application.

3.1.2 Application to a case study

The procedure described in section 2.3 is applied to three zones of Zaanstad considering one day of the week ahead. According to the specific case study, the same rule change each day or each week.

1. The input data are defined in section 2.3.1
2. The number of people is estimated for each part of the day within each day for the week ahead
3. The rule consists of displacing the occupants as described in section 2.3. In Figure 28 an example is given for three zones. The rule is aimed at displacing the building occupants in order to occupy the minimum number of thermal zones according to their maximum capacity and, when it is possible, considering the building zones with the lowest estimated energy consumption or the zones characterized by higher thermal comfort.

In Figure 28 is shown a scenario for a typical working day occupancy. The input value is the estimated total average number of occupants for each part of the day provided by the classification and regression tree in **Error! Reference source not found.** For the pilot of Zaanstad the energy ranking suggest to give priority to zone GH when predefined spatial constraints are not present. In the example reported no spatial constraints are considered.

The application of the occupants displacement strategy to the case study is developed considering different stages of analysis in the following reported:

1. Estimation of the number of occupants is performed for each part of the day by means of classification and regression tree;
2. evaluation of the minimum number of the thermal zone considering the expected maximum number of occupants during the whole day;
3. set of the HVAC Start/stop schedule according to the occupancy profile.

Figure 27 Classification And Regression Tree output

10/07/2014	Hour	Predicted Occupancy [n°]	Part of the day	Zone GH	Zone EF	Zone CD
	0	0	Night	-	-	-
	1			-	-	-
	2			-	-	-
	3			-	-	-
	4			-	-	-
	5			-	-	-
	6	157	Early Morning	Set point 20 C°	-	-
	7			-	-	-
	8	1185	Morning	-	Set point 20 C°	Set point 20 C°
	9			-	-	-
	10			-	-	-
	11			-	-	-
	12			-	-	-
	13			-	-	-
	14	1309	Afternoon	-	-	-
	15			-	-	-
	16			-	-	-
	17			-	-	-
	18	203	Late Afternoon	-	-	-
	19			-	-	-
	20			-	-	-
	21	0	Night	turn system off	turn system off	turn system off
	22			-	-	-
23	-			-	-	
					Max Occupancy	Energy ranking
				Zone GH	437	1
				Zone EF	454	2
				Zone CD	491	3
				Tot	1382	

Figure 28. Example of application of the inference rule

Figure 28 shows the application of the inference rule. Firstly, the estimated total number of occupants (during the morning and afternoon) is compared with the maximum capacity of each thermal zone. In this case, the estimated maximum number of persons is higher than the sum of the capacity of the two largest zone. This means that all the occupants need to be displaced in all the three zones. Instead, the group of hours of the early morning is characterized by an occupancy much lower than the capacity of each zone. For this reason it is possible to displace the occupants in order of time arrival at the workplace in a single thermal zone with the best energy rank. The zone EF and the Zone CD will be filled when the expected number of occupants overcomes the capacity of the first occupied zone.

The turning off of the HVAC system is scheduled at the same hour for the three zones. Indeed, the emptying of the thermal zones cannot be managed unless the zone are filled with employees having the same occupancy profile. For this reason the HVAC system will be turned off when the expected occupancy is null.

In this way it is possible to set different schedules for the three thermal zones trying to maximize the operating time of the zones with the best energy rank.

Of particular interest is the case of working days in which the estimated total number of occupants is less than the capacity of at least one zone. In Figure 29 is shown the scenario of a low occupancy estimated for a working day (e.g. Saturday). In this case the expected number of occupants is lower than the capacity of each thermal zone and in the early

morning/late afternoon hours no occupancy is expected. For this reason the rule suggests to occupy only the zone GH (the thermal zone with best energy rank) and to set the start/stop schedule of the HVAC system accordingly. It can be inferred that the HVAC start/stop schedule strongly depends by the total occupancy and the occupancy profile which can vary day by day.

10/07/2014	Hour	Predicted Occupancy [n°]	Part of the day	Zone GH	Zone EF	Zone CD
	0	0	Night	-	-	-
	1			-	-	-
	2			-	-	-
	3			-	-	-
	4			-	-	-
	5			-	-	-
	6	0	Early Morning	-	-	-
	7			-	-	-
	8			-	-	-
	9	248	Morning	Set point 20 C°	-	-
	10			-	-	-
	11			-	-	-
	12			-	-	-
	13			-	-	-
	14	138	Afternoon	-	-	-
	15			-	-	-
	16			-	-	-
	17			-	-	-
	18	0	Late Afternoon	turn system off	-	-
	19			-	-	-
	20			-	-	-
	21	0	Night	-	-	-
	22			-	-	-
23	-			-	-	
23	-			-	-	

Figure 29 Example of application of the inference rule

3.1.3 Impact of the action plan to the SCEAF indicators

The indicators influenced by this rule mainly refer to the reduction of the global energy consumption taking into account the thermal comfort of the occupants.

The following table presents an analysis of the indicators optimized through the specific inference rule.

1st Pillar: Political Field of Action

Indicator	Description	Effect
1.4	Medium term results for CO ₂ reduction in Municipal Buildings	Decrease of CO ₂ emissions
1.5	Medium term results for energy consumption reduction in Municipal Buildings	Decrease of energy consumption

2nd Pillar: Energy and Environmental Profile

Indicator	Description	Result
2.1	Energy consumption reduction in municipal buildings	Decrease of energy consumption
2.3	Average CO ₂ emission factor	Decrease of CO ₂ emission

3rd Pillar: Related Infrastructures and ICT

Indicator	Description	Result
3.5	Cost reduction for energy needs in the municipal buildings	Decrease of the energy cost
3.6	Existence of social media	Increase of the use of social media
3.7	Building management action plans influenced by occupants'/citizens' preferences	Increase of the number of day per weeks when social feedback is taken into consideration

3.2 Action Plan 2: Scheduling the set point temperature

This action plan can be supported by the implementation of either one of the following Inference Rules:

- Inference Rule 2: Determination of the neutral temperature according to TCV
- Inference Rule 3: Determination of the preferred temperature according to adaptive comfort model.

In the following sections, the implementation of this action plan will be described, based on each of the above inference rules. Every time this action plan is selected, both inference rules are executed. However, in order to select one of the two suggestions the methodology presented in the next chart is followed:

Figure 30. Methodology for inference rule selection

The rule selected is the one that produces a suggestion that is closer to the outdoor temperature. This ensures that the suggestion that will be implemented is the one that requires the least energy consumption of the two.

3.3 Scheduling the set point temperature through Thermal Comfort Validation

3.3.1 Description of data and building partitioning

As previously described, the theoretical calculation of the OMV index takes into consideration a series of parameters. However, the monitoring of variables such as air velocity, clothing, metabolic rate and operational temperature can be very challenging and, in the case of the OPTIMUS pilots, not feasible.

For this reason, during the OMV calculations performed by the model, the above parameters are set to specific values as defined by literature, while temperature and relative humidity were actually monitored by building sensors.

For the case of PMV, air temperature values are provided by the “Indoor temperature prediction model”, while the rest of variables are also estimated considering relevant literature.

The Thermal Comfort Validator (TCV) application is an online elaboration of the following questionnaire, that is designed to provide all necessary information for the AMV calculation, based on relevant standards [1, 2, 4].

Date	__/__/____	Time:	__:__ AM/PM	Location:	__	Gender:	MALE / FEMALE
Question 1: TEMPERATURE							
How do you rate your thermal sensation?							
Cold	Cool	Slightly cool	Neutral	Slightly warm	Warm	Hot	
How do you perceive the temperature?							
Clearly Acceptable		Just Acceptable		Just unacceptable		Clearly Unacceptable	
Do you want the room temperature?							
Higher			No change		Lower		
Question 2: WIND							
Would you like?							
More air movement			No Change		Less air movement		
Question 3: SUN							
Would you like?							
More sun			No Change		More shade		
Question 4: CLOTHING							
Circle ALL the items closest to what you are wearing at this moment:							
Shorts OR short skirt				Jeans OR other long pants OR long skirt			
Jumper AND/OR jacket				Vest OR singlet top			
Short sleeved shirt				Long sleeved shirt			
Shoes AND/OR socks				Sandals OR thongs			
Are your clothes mainly							
LIGHT		or		DARK		in color?	
Question 5: ACTIVITY							
For the last half hour have you been mainly:							
Sleeping		Sitting		Standing		Walking	

Figure 31. TCV Questionnaire

3.3.2 Application to a case study

In order to demonstrate the proposed methodology for the set point adjustment of the buildings, the different stages are graphically presented in the following paragraphs:

1. PMV Calculation. A screenshot of the PMV calculation for every hour of a week is depicted in the following Figure.

Step 1: PMV Calculation									
PREDICTED (PMV)			Air Temperature	Mean Radiant Temperature	Relative Air Velocity	Relative Humidity	Clothing	Metabolic Rate	PMV
DATE	Time		[°C]	[°C]	[m/s]	[%]	[clo]	[met]	
15-Nov	0:00	1:00	26,98	26,98	0,15	55,41	0,5	1,1	0,44
15-Nov	1:00	2:00	27,07	27,07	0,15	55,60	0,5	1,1	0,48
15-Nov	2:00	3:00	26,31	26,31	0,15	58,39	0,5	1,1	0,23
15-Nov	3:00	4:00	26,77	26,77	0,15	58,32	0,5	1,1	0,41
15-Nov	4:00	5:00	26,90	26,90	0,15	58,02	0,5	1,1	0,44
15-Nov	5:00	6:00	26,66	26,66	0,15	58,76	0,5	1,1	0,36
15-Nov	6:00	7:00	26,99	26,99	0,15	59,13	0,5	1,1	0,48
15-Nov	7:00	8:00	26,79	26,79	0,15	57,83	0,5	1,1	0,40
15-Nov	8:00	9:00	26,98	26,98	0,15	57,83	0,5	1,1	0,46
15-Nov	9:00	10:00	26,63	26,63	0,15	55,41	0,5	1,1	0,32
15-Nov	10:00	11:00	26,90	26,90	0,15	53,74	0,5	1,1	0,40
15-Nov	11:00	12:00	26,66	26,66	0,15	52,07	0,5	1,1	0,30
15-Nov	12:00	13:00	27,05	27,05	0,15	48,72	0,5	1,1	0,41
15-Nov	13:00	14:00	27,18	27,18	0,15	47,60	0,5	1,1	0,45
15-Nov	14:00	15:00	27,12	27,12	0,15	47,23	0,5	1,1	0,43
15-Nov	15:00	16:00	27,25	27,25	0,15	45,19	0,5	1,1	0,45
15-Nov	16:00	17:00	27,34	27,34	0,15	46,67	0,5	1,1	0,50
15-Nov	17:00	18:00	27,27	27,27	0,15	46,12	0,5	1,1	0,47
15-Nov	18:00	19:00	27,18	27,18	0,15	45,56	0,5	1,1	0,43
15-Nov	19:00	20:00	27,07	27,07	0,15	45,93	0,5	1,1	0,40
15-Nov	20:00	21:00	26,88	26,88	0,15	47,79	0,5	1,1	0,35
15-Nov	21:00	22:00	26,74	26,74	0,15	46,86	0,5	1,1	0,29
15-Nov	22:00	23:00	26,53	26,53	0,15	47,42	0,5	1,1	0,22
15-Nov	23:00	0:00	26,41	26,41	0,15	51,51	0,5	1,1	0,21
16-Nov	0:00	1:00	27,11	27,11	0,15	55,41	0,5	1,1	0,49
16-Nov	1:00	2:00	27,20	27,20	0,15	55,60	0,5	1,1	0,53
16-Nov	2:00	3:00	26,45	26,45	0,15	58,39	0,5	1,1	0,28
16-Nov	3:00	4:00	26,91	26,91	0,15	58,32	0,5	1,1	0,45

Figure 32. PMV Calculation

2. AMV retrieval by TCV Web App. As explained in previous paragraphs, the feedback from users refers to the comfort level of the exact time completed the questionnaire, expanded before and after by a certain time interval.

Figure 33. TCV feedback expanded effect

The collection and evaluation of the questionnaires' feedback is a dynamic and continuous process, leading to the aggregated assessment of thermal comfort for each hour and day of the week, by graphically adding results per hourly time-slot.

Step 2: AMV Definition: Feedback from TCV Web App																					
ACTUAL (AMV)		User 1	User 2	User 3	User 4	User 5	User 6	User 7	User 8	User 9	User 10	User 11	User 12	User 13	User 14	User 15	User 16	User 17	User 18	User 19	User 20
Time																					
0:00	1:00																				
1:00	2:00																				
2:00	3:00																				
3:00	4:00																				
4:00	5:00							-0,5													
5:00	6:00	-0,5						-1,0													
6:00	7:00	-1,0		-0,5				-1,5					-0,5								
7:00	8:00	-1,5	-0,5		-1,0	-0,5		-2,0					-1,0								
8:00	9:00	-2,0	-1,0	-0,5	-1,5	-1,0	-0,5	-2,5		-0,5		-0,5	-1,5								
9:00	10:00	-1,5	-0,5	-1,0	-2,0	-0,5	-1,0	-3,0		-1,0		-1,0	-2,0								
10:00	11:00	-1,0	-0,5	-1,5	-1,5	-1,5	-2,5	-0,5	-1,5	-0,5	-0,5	-1,5									
11:00	12:00	-0,5		-1,0		-2,0	-2,0	-1,0	-2,0	-1,0		-1,0									
12:00	13:00			-0,5		-1,5	-1,5	-0,5	-1,5	-0,5		-0,5									
13:00	14:00					-1,0	-1,0		-1,0												
14:00	15:00					-0,5	-0,5		-0,5												
15:00	16:00																				
16:00	17:00																				
17:00	18:00													-0,5	-0,5						
18:00	19:00													-1,0	-1,0						
19:00	20:00													-1,5	-1,5		-0,5				
20:00	21:00													-2,0	-2,0	-0,5	-1,0				
21:00	22:00													-1,5	-1,5	-1,0	-0,5				
22:00	23:00													-1,0	-1,0	-0,5					
23:00	0:00													-0,5	-0,5						
0:00	1:00																				
1:00	2:00																				
2:00	3:00																				
3:00	4:00																				

Figure 34. AMV retrieval by TCV Web App

3. AMV Filtering. In order to ensure that no invalid input will be taken into consideration, an additional filter regarding the reliability of the inputs collected is applied on the aggregated score of each day.

More filters can be applied at this stage, in order to ensure that indoor conditions will remain within acceptable limits, according to relevant standards outlining lower and upper limits of acceptable conditions.

Step 2: AMV Definition: Feedback from TCV Web App																						Step 3: AMV Filtering			
ACTUAL (AMV)		User 1	User 2	User 3	User 4	User 5	User 6	User 7	User 8	User 9	User 10	User 11	User 12	User 13	User 14	User 15	User 16	User 17	User 18	User 19	User 20	Average	Operational Issues?	Top-Up/Reboil?	AMV
Time																									
0:00	1:00																					-	0	0	
1:00	2:00																					-	0	0	
2:00	3:00																					-	0	0	
3:00	4:00																					-	0	0	
4:00	5:00																					1	-0.50	0	0
5:00	6:00																					2	-0.75	0	0
6:00	7:00																					4	-0.88	0	0
7:00	8:00																					6	-1.08	0	0
8:00	9:00																					10	-1.15	Yes	-1.15
9:00	10:00																					10	-1.35	Yes	-1.35
10:00	11:00																					10	-1.15	Yes	-1.15
11:00	12:00																					8	-1.31	Yes	-1.31
12:00	13:00																					7	-0.93	Yes	-0.93
13:00	14:00																					3	-1.00	Yes	-1.00
14:00	15:00																					3	-0.50	Yes	-0.50
15:00	16:00																					0	NA	No	NA
16:00	17:00																					0	NA	No	NA
17:00	18:00																					2	-0.50	No	NA
18:00	19:00																					2	-1.00	No	NA
19:00	20:00																					3	-1.17	Yes	-1.17
20:00	21:00																					4	-1.38	Yes	-1.38
21:00	22:00																					4	-1.13	0	0
22:00	23:00																					3	-0.83	0	0
23:00	0:00																					2	-0.50	0	0
0:00	1:00																					0	-	0	0
1:00	2:00																					0	-	0	0
2:00	3:00																					0	-	0	0
3:00	4:00																					0	-	0	0

Figure 35. AMV Filtering

3. **OMV Calculation.** The OMV is calculated based on monitored indoor conditions:

Step 4: OMV Calculation									
OBSERVED (OMV)		Air Temperature	Mean Radiant Temperature	Air Velocity	Relative Humidity	Clothing	Metabolic Rate	OMV	
Time		[°C]	[°C]	[m/s]	[%]	[clo]	[met]		
0:00	1:00	26,44	26,44	0,15	55,41	0,5	1,1	0,25	
1:00	2:00	26,53	26,53	0,15	55,60	0,5	1,1	0,29	
2:00	3:00	25,79	25,79	0,15	58,39	0,5	1,1	0,05	
3:00	4:00	26,24	26,24	0,15	59,32	0,5	1,1	0,21	
4:00	5:00	26,36	26,36	0,15	58,02	0,5	1,1	0,25	
5:00	6:00	26,13	26,13	0,15	58,76	0,5	1,1	0,17	
6:00	7:00	26,43	26,43	0,15	59,13	0,5	1,1	0,29	
7:00	8:00	26,26	26,26	0,15	57,83	0,5	1,1	0,21	
8:00	9:00	26,44	26,44	0,15	57,83	0,5	1,1	0,27	
9:00	10:00	26,09	26,09	0,15	55,41	0,5	1,1	0,13	
10:00	11:00	26,36	26,36	0,15	53,74	0,5	1,1	0,21	
11:00	12:00	26,13	26,13	0,15	52,07	0,5	1,1	0,12	
12:00	13:00	26,51	26,51	0,15	48,72	0,5	1,1	0,22	
13:00	14:00	26,63	26,63	0,15	47,60	0,5	1,1	0,26	
14:00	15:00	26,58	26,58	0,15	47,23	0,5	1,1	0,23	
15:00	16:00	26,71	26,71	0,15	45,19	0,5	1,1	0,26	
16:00	17:00	26,80	26,80	0,15	46,67	0,5	1,1	0,31	
17:00	18:00	26,72	26,72	0,15	46,12	0,5	1,1	0,28	
18:00	19:00	26,63	26,63	0,15	45,56	0,5	1,1	0,24	
19:00	20:00	26,53	26,53	0,15	45,93	0,5	1,1	0,20	
20:00	21:00	26,35	26,35	0,15	47,79	0,5	1,1	0,16	
21:00	22:00	26,20	26,20	0,15	46,86	0,5	1,1	0,10	
22:00	23:00	26,00	26,00	0,15	47,42	0,5	1,1	0,03	
23:00	0:00	25,88	25,88	0,15	51,51	0,5	1,1	0,02	
0:00	1:00	26,57	26,57	0,15	55,41	0,5	1,1	0,30	
1:00	2:00	26,66	26,66	0,15	55,60	0,5	1,1	0,33	
2:00	3:00	25,92	25,92	0,15	58,39	0,5	1,1	0,09	
3:00	4:00	26,37	26,37	0,15	59,32	0,5	1,1	0,26	

Figure 36. OMV Calculation

4. **Correlation calculation between AMV-OMV.** AMV and corresponding OMV values serve as data points that form a plot. Their correlation is expressed via a linear equation.

Figure 37. Correlation between AMV-OMV

5. **Definition of OMV value that corresponds to AMV=0,** based on the previous equation:

For AMV=0, **OMV=0,8513**

6. **Definition of the temperature value that corresponds to this OMV.**

This step produces the final outcome of the action plan, which a temperature set-point suggestion for the following week.

Step 7: Find the temperature that gives this OMV (by solving the PMV⁻¹ equation, with all the other values considered as the average of weekly data)

Air Temperature	Mean Radiant Temperature	Relative Air Velocity	Relative Humidity	Clothing	Metabolic Rate	OMV
28,20	8,20	0,15	52,004	0,5	1,1	0,851

Figure 38. Definition of the temperature value that corresponds to OMV of Step 6

7. AMV Validation

Step 1: PMV Calculation									Step 9: AMV Validation	
PREDICTED (PMV)		Air Temperature	Mean Radiant Temperature	Relative Air Velocity	Relative Humidity	Clothing	Metabolic Rate	PMV	AMV for this PMV	ASHRAE 55 (Category B: -0.5 < PMV < 0.5)
Time		[°C]	[°C]	[m/s]	[%]	[clo]	[met]			
0:00	1:00	26.98	26.98	0.15	55.41	0.5	1.1	0.44	-0.29	Acceptable
1:00	2:00	27.07	27.07	0.15	55.60	0.5	1.1	0.48	-0.23	Acceptable
2:00	3:00	26.31	26.31	0.15	58.39	0.5	1.1	0.23	-0.65	Change set point
3:00	4:00	26.77	26.77	0.15	58.32	0.5	1.1	0.41	-0.36	Acceptable
4:00	5:00	26.90	26.90	0.15	58.02	0.5	1.1	0.44	-0.30	Acceptable
5:00	6:00	26.66	26.66	0.15	58.76	0.5	1.1	0.36	-0.44	Acceptable
6:00	7:00	26.99	26.99	0.15	58.13	0.5	1.1	0.45	-0.23	Acceptable
7:00	8:00	26.79	26.79	0.15	57.83	0.5	1.1	0.40	-0.37	Acceptable
8:00	9:00	26.88	26.88	0.15	57.83	0.5	1.1	0.46	-0.26	Acceptable
9:00	10:00	26.63	26.63	0.15	55.41	0.5	1.1	0.32	-0.51	Change set point
10:00	11:00	26.90	26.90	0.15	55.74	0.5	1.1	0.40	-0.36	Acceptable
11:00	12:00	26.66	26.66	0.15	52.07	0.5	1.1	0.30	-0.53	Change set point
12:00	13:00	27.05	27.05	0.15	48.72	0.5	1.1	0.41	-0.35	Acceptable
13:00	14:00	27.18	27.18	0.15	47.60	0.5	1.1	0.45	-0.29	Acceptable
14:00	15:00	27.12	27.12	0.15	47.23	0.5	1.1	0.43	-0.32	Acceptable
15:00	16:00	27.25	27.25	0.15	45.19	0.5	1.1	0.45	-0.28	Acceptable
16:00	17:00	27.34	27.34	0.15	46.67	0.5	1.1	0.50	-0.20	Acceptable
17:00	18:00	27.27	27.27	0.15	46.12	0.5	1.1	0.47	-0.25	Acceptable
18:00	19:00	27.18	27.18	0.15	45.56	0.5	1.1	0.43	-0.32	Acceptable
19:00	20:00	27.07	27.07	0.15	45.93	0.5	1.1	0.40	-0.38	Acceptable
20:00	21:00	26.88	26.88	0.15	47.79	0.5	1.1	0.35	-0.46	Acceptable
21:00	22:00	26.74	26.74	0.15	46.86	0.5	1.1	0.29	-0.56	Change set point
22:00	23:00	26.53	26.53	0.15	47.42	0.5	1.1	0.22	-0.68	Change set point
23:00	0:00	26.41	26.41	0.15	51.51	0.5	1.1	0.21	-0.70	Change set point
0:00	1:00	27.11	27.11	0.15	55.41	0.5	1.1	0.49	-0.21	Acceptable
1:00	2:00	27.20	27.20	0.15	55.60	0.5	1.1	0.53	-0.15	Acceptable
2:00	3:00	26.45	26.45	0.15	58.39	0.5	1.1	0.28	-0.57	Change set point
3:00	4:00	26.91	26.91	0.15	58.32	0.5	1.1	0.45	-0.28	Acceptable

Figure 39. AMV Validation

The analytical work flow is available in the following Figure:

Figure 40. Work flow of the set point adjustment methodology

An additional functionality of this action plan is that it can reveal possible need for maintenance. Thermal Comfort standards are developed to ensure that the majority of the building occupants are within the comfort levels, regardless their age, gender and mobility etc. Therefore, if it is observed that users systematically feel discomfort, even when the OMV is within acceptable levels, then this could suggest the existence of one of the following problems:

- Failure of the monitoring system - sensors
- Need for maintenance of the HVAC system
- Thermal losses via the distribution system or the building envelope.

The above reasons should be customized according to the profile and existing systems of the building under examination. If a large number of unacceptable feedbacks is reported, the system may propose a maintenance check.

3.4 Scheduling the set point temperature according to the adaptive comfort concept

3.4.1 Description of data and building partitioning

As previously described, the data needed for the development of the rule are related to the forecast of the outdoor air temperature. In Table 10 the list of data is shown.

Table 10. Input data and source of acquisition for the Sant Cugat Town Hall

Input Data	Measurement units	Source	Spatial scale
Temperature	°C	Local weather station (tbc)	-
Month	-	DSS Engine	-
Hour	-	DSS Engine	-

3.4.2 Application to a case study

Sant Cugat Town Hall and Theatre

This rule has been applied to Sant Cugat. The outdoor air temperature was collected from October 2014 until March 2015. According to the calculation procedure described in section 2.5 the running mean temperature has been calculated together with the scheduled set point temperature.

In Figure 35 the set point temperature versus the running mean outdoor temperature is shown. According to the adaptive comfort approach, the set point temperature suggested for the heating period is 21,5°C except for few hours characterized by a higher running mean outdoor temperature.

Figure 41. Set point temperature vs running mean outside temperature (October 2014 – March 2015, Sant Cugat)

3.4.3 Impact of the action plan to the SCEAF indicators

In the following tables an analysis of the SCEAF indicators optimized through the specific action plan is presented.

1st Pillar: Political Field of Action

Indicator	Description	Result
1.4	Medium term results for CO ₂ reduction in Municipal Buildings	Decrease of CO ₂ emissions
1.5	Medium term results for energy consumption reduction in Municipal Buildings	Reduction of energy consumption

2nd Pillar: Energy and Environmental Profile

Indicator	Description	Result
2.1	Energy consumption reduction in municipal buildings	Reduction of energy consumption
2.2	Percentage reduction of fossil fuels	Reduction of fossil fuels consumption
2.3	Average CO ₂ emission factor	The total energy consumption is decreased (denominator), as well as the proportion of each energy carrier in the mix.

3rd Pillar: Related Infrastructures and ICT

Indicator	Description	Result
3.3	Forecasting systems	Additional forecasting system used within the building
3.5	Cost reduction for energy needs (gas, petroleum and electricity) in the municipal building	Decrease of energy consumption, leads to the avoidance of costs of fuel purchase
3.6	Existence of social media (Facebook, twitter)	Increase of social media accounts used for the municipal buildings
3.7	Building management action plans influenced by occupants'/ inhabitants'/ citizens' preferences	Action plans are influenced by users' feedback

3.5 Action Plan 3: Scheduling the on/off of the heating system

This Action Plan is mainly based on Inference Rule 4: Determination of the optimum start/stop of the heating system. However, it can also employ Inference Rule 2: Determination of the neutral temperature according to TCV or Inference Rule 3: Determination of the preferred temperature according to adaptive comfort model, depending on whether the Action Plan of Set-Point Management is applied, as described above. In case it is applied, Inference Rules 2 or 3 will provide the parameter of Indoor air temperature.

The Action Plan of Scheduling the on/off of the heating system is applied to a single zone (office) in the Town Hall of Sant Cugat.

3.5.1 Description of data and building partitioning

In Table 11 the input data for the implementation of the inference rule are listed.

Table 11. Listing of the input variable

Input variable	Units	Source	Spatial scale
Occupied/ unoccupied space	-	DSS Engine	Building zone
On/off heating/cooling system scheduling	-	DSS Engine	Building zone
Space heating/cooling capacity	W	DSS Engine	Building zone
Outdoor air temperature	°C	Local weather station (tbc)	-
Energy consumption	kWh	On-site monitoring system (ENERGEA Monitoring software, via the energy production data- capturing module)	Building zone
Indoor air temperature	°C		Building zone

In Figure 36 the building partitioning related to both monitored zones and zone subject to action are presented according to D2.1.

Monitored zone. Building partitioning 1: Indoor air temperature, occupied/unoccupied space, system on/off, system capacity

Monitored zone. Building partitioning 2: energy consumption

Zone subject to action.

Figure 42. Building partitioning Sant Cugat

3.5.2 Application to a case study

This rule is applied to a zone of Sant Cugat Town Hall.

As described in D3.2, the indoor air temperature prediction model was first applied to the Sant Cugat Town Hall using the collected data of 4 months of the heating period between 2014 and 2015. The indoor air temperature was collected for one zone of the Town Hall (Zone 1(A) – CZ1.1 – F3 in Figure 42) while the outdoor air temperature was collected from a nearby weather station.

The regressors (Φ/H and τ) were found and the predictive model was applied. This rule consists of defining the optimum start of the heating system according to the forecast outdoor air temperature and the predicted occupancy profile of the zone. In the following the application of the procedure is described.

1. The occupancy profile for the week after is recorded. For each hour and each zone it must be clear whether the zone is occupied or not. In Figure 43 an example is shown: the space is occupied from 8 am until 6 pm for a typical working day.

Figure 43. Occupancy profile for a typical working day

2. The predicted hourly outdoor air temperature is given for the entire week.

3. Once the predicted indoor air temperature of a zone has been calculated according to the procedure above, the last day/s of the week before can be considered as the starting point for the week after. In Figure 44 the last two days of the week before (Saturday and Sunday) are shown considering a cut-off mode (period 1).

Figure 44. Predicted indoor air temperature of the

4. The boost time is calculated according to the procedure described.

Figure 45. Indoor air temperature trend

5. Once t_0 is calculated, the indoor air temperature for period 2 is calculated through equation 4.

Figure 46. Indoor air temperature trend for period 1 and 2

6. The boost period ends when the indoor air temperature is equal to the set point temperature.

7. The normal heating operation ends when the zone is unoccupied (at 7 pm in Figure 43) and the heating system is turned off.

A first indoor air temperature trend is calculated as shown in Figure 47 (dotted blue line).

Figure 47. Indoor air temperature trend for periods 2, 3 and 4

8. The boost time and the indoor air temperature trend of period 4 is calculated.

Figure 48. Indoor air temperature trend for periods 2, 3 and 4

Once t_0 of period 4 is calculated, the calculation of the indoor air temperature of period 3 must be repeated considering a new value of θ_e .

9. The calculation of the indoor air temperature trend both for period 3 and 4 must be calculated until $\theta_{i,n+1} = \theta_{i,n} \pm 0,5^\circ\text{C}$

The calculation procedure must be repeated from point 6 for the rest of the week.

3.5.3 Impact of the action plan to the SCEAF indicators

In the following tables an analysis of the SCEAF indicators optimized through the specific action plan is presented.

1st Pillar: Political Field of Action

Indicator	Description	Result
1.4	Medium term results for CO ₂ reduction in Municipal Buildings	Decrease of CO ₂ emissions
1.5	Medium term results for energy consumption reduction in Municipal Buildings	Reduction of energy consumption

2nd Pillar: Energy and Environmental Profile

Indicator	Description	Result
2.1	Energy consumption reduction in municipal buildings	Reduction of energy consumption
2.2	Percentage reduction of fossil fuels	Reduction of fossil fuels consumption
2.3	Average CO ₂ emission factor	The total energy consumption is decreased (denominator), as well as the proportion of each energy carrier in the mix.

3rd Pillar: Related Infrastructures and ICT

Indicator	Description	Result
3.3	Forecasting systems	Additional forecasting system used within the building
3.5	Cost reduction for energy needs (gas, petroleum and electricity) in the municipal building	Decrease of energy consumption, leads to the avoidance of costs of fuel purchase

3.6 Action Plan 4: Management of the air-side economizer

3.6.1 Description of data and building partitioning

This Action Plan is based on *Inference Rule 5: Assessing the free cooling options* and has been applied to Sant Cugat Town Hall. The indoor air temperature trend for zone Zone 1(A) – CZ1.1 – F3 (see Figure 42) together with the outdoor air temperature and relative humidity was collected for a period including the middle seasons and the summer season of 2014 where a potential of an air side economizer mode can exist.

In Table 12 the input data for the implementation of the inference rule are listed.

Table 12. Listing of the input variable

Input variable	Units	Source	Spatial scale
Outdoor air temperature	°C	Local weather station (tbc)	-
Relative humidity	%	Local weather station (tbc)	-
Indoor air temperature	°C	On-site monitoring system (ENERGEA Monitoring software, via the energy production data-capturing module)	Building zone

In Figure 49 the building partitioning related to monitored zones is shown. No building partitioning is needed for the action since the management of the air side economizer will be at building level.

Figure 49. Building partitioning Sant Cugat

3.6.2 Application to a case study

A first application of the rule was performed for Sant Cugat Town Hall. As mentioned above, both the outdoor climatic data and the indoor air temperature were collected for a period from June 12 until October 18.

The rule has been applied considering both the temperature and the enthalpy of the outdoor air as control parameters. Moreover, the outdoor air temperature has been compared to the indoor air temperature (whose temperature is considered to be equal to the recirculating air) and to an assigned threshold value fixed to 23 °C, considered as an acceptable value for the management of air side economizer.

The comparison has been performed for both a period of 24 hours per day, and for the working time. The first hypothesis is due to the possibility of using the air side economizer also during the night period, activating an overcooling of the indoor environment.

In the following, a frequency analysis of both outdoor temperature and enthalpy is presented for Sant Cugat in order to demonstrate the existing potentiality to operate in economizer conditions.

Figures 50 and 51 show that about 60% of the hours are characterized by temperature lower than 23°C; and about 40% are characterized by an enthalpy lower than 52,5 kJ/kg (the enthalpy of the indoor air temperature at 24°C and relative humidity equal to 50%).

The possibility of overcooling the building during the night time is feasible due to the low temperatures that occurs in Sant Cugat (20 °C on average between midnight and 6 am, considering both middle season and summer seasons). Due to lower temperatures and the lower prices of energy during the night, it is very likely that the shifting of the cooling to the night hours leads to a higher share of free cooling.

Figure 50. Outdoor air temperature frequency considering a period of 24 hours per day

Figure 51. Outdoor air enthalpy frequency considering a period of 24 hours per day

Figures 52 and 53 show that more than 40% of the hours between 6 am and 7 pm are characterized by temperature lower than 23°C; and more than 30% are characterized by an enthalpy lower than 52,5 kJ/kg (the enthalpy of the indoor air temperature at 24°C and relative humidity equal to 50%).

Figure 52. Outdoor air temperature frequency considering a period of 14 hours per day

Figure 53. Outdoor air enthalpy frequency considering a period of 14 hours per day

3.6.3 Impact of the action plan to the SCEAF indicators

In the following tables an analysis of the SCEAF indicators optimized through the specific action plan is presented.

1st Pillar: Political Field of Action

Indicator	Description	Result
1.4	Medium term results for CO ₂ reduction in Municipal Buildings	Decrease of CO ₂ emissions
1.5	Medium term results for energy consumption reduction in Municipal Buildings	Reduction of energy consumption

2nd Pillar: Energy and Environmental Profile

Indicator	Description	Result
2.1	Energy consumption reduction in municipal buildings	Reduction of energy consumption
2.2	Percentage reduction of fossil fuels	Reduction of fossil fuels consumption
2.3	Average CO ₂ emission factor	The total energy consumption is decreased (denominator), as well as the proportion of each energy carrier in the mix.

3rd Pillar: Related Infrastructures and ICT

Indicator	Description	Result
3.3	Forecasting systems	Additional forecasting system used within the building
3.5	Cost reduction for energy needs (gas, petroleum and electricity) in the municipal building	Decrease of energy consumption, leads to the avoidance of costs of fuel purchase

3.7 Action Plan 5: Scheduling the PV maintenance

3.7.1 Description of data and building partitioning

This Action Plan is based on ***Inference Rule 6: Evaluating the electricity production of the PV system to check possible faults.***

As described in D3.2, PV production is forecasted for each hour of the day individually using a unique MLR model. This is mainly done in order to better model the influential effect of each time on the dependent variable, leading to the minimum Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) and insignificant bias. According to the methodological framework proposed in D3.2, PV MLR models were built for the pilot cases of Sant Cugat and Savona, where PV installations exist, and the PV maintenance rule was accordingly applied.

Sant Cugat Pilot Case

In order to estimate the MLR model of the Sant Cugat case, a training sample of 1 year (2385 hours of non-zero production) from 17th April 2014 to 17th April 2015 was used, which includes the weather conditions of the PV plant and its hourly production in Watts. The PV production data were collected by the on-site monitoring system of the Town Hall, while the weather data were mined by the database of a nearby weather station. A list of the collected variables is presented in the Table 13.

Table 13. Input data and source of acquisition for the Sant Cugat Town Hall

Input Data	Measurement units	Source	Spatial scale
Energy production	W	On-site monitoring system (ENERGEA Monitoring software, via the energy production data-capturing module)	Entire building
Temperature	°C	Local weather station (tbc)	-
Humidity	-	Local weather station (tbc)	-
Pressure	Pa	Local weather station (tbc)	-
Wind Direction Degrees	-	Local weather station (tbc)	-
Solar Radiation	W/m ²	Local weather station (tbc)	-
Dew point	°C	Local weather station (tbc)	-
Wind Speed	Km/h	Local weather station (tbc)	-
Month	-	DSS Engine	-
Hour	-	DSS Engine	-

As an example, the predicted PV production (red line) compared to the actual values (black line) for 100 random observations of the Sant Cugat Town Hall data set is illustrated in the following Figure. As seen, in this specific sample there is a total number of 4 alarms (purple bubbles) since the actual production was outside the ranges set by the prediction intervals (green lines). However, in the total evaluation of the PV plant, no maintenance actions – alerts- would be proposed since there is no systematic evidence of failure.

Figure 54. The predicted (red line) and the original (black line) PV production for 100 random observations of the Sant Cugat Town Hall data set. Hourly alarms are plotted using the purple points.

3.7.2 Application to a case study

Sant Cugat Pilot Case

In the case of Sant Cugat, soiling and wear of the equipment was detected in practice in the given data set. A total amount of 1348 hourly alarms were recorded, specifically:

- 357 in 2012
- 406 in 2013
- 585 in 2014.

As seen in Figure 49, there is a significant trend on the number of alarms produced per month and the ageing-soiling of the equipment seems to be strongly correlated with them. Therefore, the proposed solution would possibly make a significant change in the management of the PV facility.

Figure 55. PV alarms per month

3.7.3 Impact of the action plan to the SCEAF indicators

By considering PV energy production as a milestone towards energy optimization, energy performance and SCEAF indicators can be further improved. Indicators that are identified to be influenced by such an action plan mainly refer to the reduction of fossil fuel consumption, increase of renewables in the final energy use and consequent emission reduction, or to an update of the Related Infrastructures of the building:

In the following table an analysis of the indicators optimized through the specific action plan is presented.

1st Pillar: Political Field of Action

Indicator	Description	Result
1.4	Medium term results for CO ₂ reduction in Municipal Buildings	Decrease of CO ₂ emissions
1.6	Medium term results for renewable energy sources in the final use in Municipal Buildings	Increase of renewable energy in the final energy use mix

2nd Pillar: Energy and Environmental Profile

Indicator	Description	Result
2.2	Percentage reduction of fossil fuels	Increase of renewables in energy mix, leading to a percentage decrease of fossil fuels
2.3	Average CO ₂ emission factor	Increase of renewables in energy mix, leading to a lower average emission factor

Indicator	Description	Result
2.4	Renewable Energy Sources (RES) production intensity	Increase of renewables in energy mix

3rd Pillar: Related Infrastructures and ICT

Indicator	Description	Result
3.3	Forecasting systems	Additional forecasting system used within the building
3.5	Cost reduction for energy needs (gas, petroleum and electricity) in the municipal building	Increase of renewables in energy mix, leading to a decrease of fossil fuels use, hence to the avoidance of costs of fuel purchase

3.8 Action Plan 6: Scheduling of the sale/consumption of the electricity produced through the PV system

3.8.1 Description of data and building partitioning

This Action Plan is based on **Inference Rule 7: Shifting electrical loads to optimize PV performance**. The strategies described in D2.9 are aimed to optimize PV performance through the shifting of the electrical loads during the day. The three inference rules (green, finance, peak) are set on the trend of energy market in order to maximize the energy self-used, maximize the income from the energy sale or to not overcome a threshold of net average power demand for increasing the load factor. For the different objectives, the inference rules are based on demand side management strategies.

3.8.2 Application to a case study

The three strategies are based on the evaluation, using prediction models, of hourly energy demand profile, hourly energy generated by PV, selling price of energy produced by PV system and purchase cost of energy from the grid. The scope of these strategies is to suggest recommendations to supervise the load shifting following the daily energy market (see Figure 56).

Figure 56. Energy prices

In the pilot of Sant Cugat as it is possible to verify in the following figure, the PV system is undersized in comparison to electrical energy demand. For this reason in order to show all the potentialities of the developed inference rule an upgraded PV system capable to produce a higher energy generation profile was considered. The demand energy profile instead was derived from the monitoring data available for the pilot.

Figure 57. Real energy Profiles 10/07/2014

In order to demonstrate the proposed methodology discussed in the section 2.9 for the use/selling of self-produced energy by PV, the different stages are graphically presented in the following sections.

3.8.2.1 Application to a case study (green strategy)

The green strategy is aimed to maximize the self-using of energy produced by PV considering the daily energy market. This strategy includes actions (load shifting) only during the hours in which a surplus of energy produced by PV over the energy demand occurs. In particular the rule suggests to sale energy only during the surplus hours with a positive price check. On the other hand during the surplus hours with a negative price check, the rule promotes the self-using of energy produced by PV through the load shifting in these hours.

In the following the application of the green strategy to the case study is developed considering different stages of analysis.

1. Price check

A price check is performed for each hour of the day as shown in Figure 58. This step makes it possible to evaluate the hours with positive/negative price check.

Hour	Energy sell price [€/kWh]	Energy purchase price [€/kWh]	Energy generation from PV [kWh]	price check
0	0.05	0.0302	0	True
1	0.05	0.02762	0	True
2	0.05	0.02546	0	True
3	0.05	0.02549	0	True
4	0.05	0.02478	0	True
5	0.05	0.02543	0	True
6	0.05	0.029	0	True
7	0.05	0.03293	0	True
8	0.05	0.04126	2.886404055	True
9	0.05	0.04417	23.01299261	True
10	0.05	0.04495	75.87412397	True
11	0.05	0.04417	126.6300608	True
12	0.05	0.04495	163.7916834	True
13	0.05	0.0454	188.5884912	True
14	0.05	0.04417	200.3850726	True
15	0.05	0.04417	201.5574482	True
16	0.04	0.04417	189.5027356	False
17	0.04	0.0446	166.3215259	False
18	0.04	0.046	145.7273393	False
19	0.05	0.04417	73.667642	True
20	0.05	0.04417	30.47022708	True
21	0.05	0.04658	5.385637364	True
22	0.05	0.04719	0.459896307	True
23	0.05	0.04417	0	True

Figure 58. Price check green strategy

2. Inference rule

In this step surplus hours with the correspondent price check are evaluated. In these hours if the price check is positive, it is convenient to sell the surplus of energy produced by PV. If the price check is negative, instead it is more convenient to try to use all the energy produced by PV. To this purpose a message for promoting a shifting of the electrical loads during these hours appears.

Energy surplus [kWh]	price check	inference rule
0.0	True	-
11.0	True	Sell energy surplus
20.5	False	Try to shift electric load
11.9	False	Try to shift electric load
20.5	False	Try to shift electric load
24.2	True	Sell energy surplus
0.0	True	-

Figure 59. Inference rule green strategy

In order to quantify the effect of the inference rule the daily energy used from PV with and without the application of inference rule is calculated (Figure 64 - Figure 65). Moreover, a calculation of the economic income related to the selling of energy is carried out. If the DMS

Hour	Energy sell price [€/kWh]	Energy purchase price [€/kWh]	Energy generation from PV [kWh]	Energy Demand [kWh]	price check
0	0,09	0,0302	0	50,078	VERO
1	0,09	0,02762	0	51,679	VERO
2	0,09	0,02546	0	61,066	VERO
3	0,09	0,02549	0	81,649	VERO
4	0,09	0,02478	0	135,16	VERO
5	0,09	0,02543	0	159,786	VERO
6	0,09	0,029	0	206,349	VERO
7	0,09	0,03293	0	203,045	VERO
8	0,09	0,04126	2,886404055	241,261	VERO
9	0,09	0,04417	23,01399261	243,347	VERO
10	0,09	0,04495	75,87412397	252	VERO
11	0,09	0,04417	126,6300608	284,82	VERO
12	0,09	0,04495	163,7916834	252,602	VERO
13	0,09	0,0454	188,5884912	239	VERO
14	0,09	0,04417	200,3850726	227,405	VERO
15	0,09	0,04417	201,5574482	190,521	VERO
16	0,09	0,04417	189,5027366	168,957	FALSO
17	0,09	0,0446	166,3215259	154,415	FALSO
18	0,09	0,046	145,7273393	125,212	FALSO
19	0,09	0,04417	73,667642	49,496	VERO
20	0,09	0,04417	30,47022708	50,526	VERO
21	0,09	0,04658	5,385637364	49,17	VERO
22	0,09	0,04719	0,459896307	51,152	VERO
23	0,09	0,04417	0	48,919	VERO

Figure 62. Price check finance strategy

2. Inference rule

In this phase surplus hours with negative and positive price check, and hours in which a surplus of energy can be created, are evaluated. The rule suggests to sell energy during the surplus hours with positive price check, to create a surplus during the potential surplus hours shifting the loads in the surplus hours with negative price check.

Energy surplus [kWh]	price check	potential surplus hours	inference rule
0.0	VERO	-	-
0.0	VERO	-	-
0.0	VERO	-	-
0.0	VERO	-	-
0.0	VERO	-	-
0.0	VERO	-	-
0.0	VERO	-	-
0.0	VERO	-	-
0.0	VERO	-	-
0.0	VERO	-	-
0.0	VERO	-	-
0.0	VERO	-	-
0.0	VERO	-	-
0.0	VERO	-	-
0.0	VERO	potential surplus	try to create a surplus
11.0	VERO	-	sell energy surplus
20.5	FALSO	-	try to shift electric load
11.9	FALSO	-	try to shift electric load
20.5	FALSO	-	try to shift electric load
24.2	VERO	-	sell energy surplus
0.0	VERO	-	-
0.0	VERO	-	-
0.0	VERO	-	-
0.0	VERO	-	-

Figure 63. Inference rule finance strategy

In order to quantify the effect of the inference rule the income from the selling of energy with and without the application of inference rule is calculated (Figure 64 - Figure 65). If the DMS strategies can be implemented as suggested by inference rule the income from the selling of energy increases from 3,9 € to 4,4 €.

on the capacity to receive shifted energy of the no peak hours with low energy purchase cost of energy.

The methodological steps are list below:

1. Price check

A price check is performed for each hour of the day as shown in Figure 66. This step allows to evaluate the hours with a positive or negative price check.

Hour	Energy sell price [€/kWh]	Energy purchase price [€/kWh]	Energy generation from PV [kWh]	Energy Demand [kWh]	Price check
0	0.05	0.0302	0	50.078	True
1	0.05	0.02762	0	51.679	True
2	0.05	0.02546	0	61.066	True
3	0.05	0.02549	0	81.649	True
4	0.05	0.02478	0	135.16	True
5	0.05	0.03293	0	159.786	True
6	0.05	0.03293	0	206.349	True
7	0.05	0.03293	0	223.045	True
8	0.05	0.04126	2.886404055	241.261	True
9	0.04	0.04417	23.01299261	243.347	False
10	0.04	0.04495	75.87412397	252	False
11	0.05	0.04417	126.6300608	284.82	True
12	0.04	0.04495	163.7916834	252.602	False
13	0.04	0.0454	188.5884912	239	False
14	0.04	0.04417	220.3850726	227.405	False
15	0.05	0.04417	201.5574482	190.521	True
16	0.022	0.02478	189.5027366	168.957	False
17	0.04	0.04417	166.3215259	154.415	False
18	0.04	0.02549	145.7273393	125.212	True
19	0.04	0.02478	73.667642	49.496	True
20	0.04	0.02543	30.47022708	50.526	True
21	0.05	0.04658	5.385637364	49.17	True
22	0.05	0.04719	0.459896307	51.152	True
23	0.05	0.04417	0	48.919	True

Figure 66. Price check peak strategy

2. Inference rule

In this phase surplus hours with negative and positive price check, and extra demand hours are evaluated. Firstly, the rule suggests to sell the energy during surplus hours with positive price check. The second step is evaluate the extra demand $((E_{dem}-E_{gen})^+-E^*)^+$ during the peak hours (Figure 67). The threshold E^* selected in the application corresponds to the 85th percentile of the $(E_{dem}-E_{gen})^+$ daily profile.

Figure 67 $(E_{dem}-E_{gen})^+$ daily profile

In the following example The Threshold is 193 kWh, the extra demand is 117 kWh (considering in period 6:00-9:00). The rule suggests first to shift a part of the extra demand to cover the surplus of energy (32 kWh) in the hours with negative price check. The residual extra demand (85 kWh) should be shifted in the hours with the lowest purchase cost of energy as suggested by the inference rule (Figure 68). The algorithm suggests automatically these hours also considering the maximum energy that is possible to shift in for each of them.

Energy purchase price [€/kWh]	(Edem-Egen)* [kWh]	Extra demand [kWh]	Energy surplus [kWh]	Price check	Inference rule (1)	Inference rule (2)	maximum capacity
0.0302	50.08	0	0	True	-	-	142.67
0.02762	51.68	0	0	True	-	-	141.07
0.02546	61.07	0	0	True	-	Shift electric load here	131.68
0.02549	81.65	0	0	True	-	-	111.10
0.02478	135.16	0	0	True	-	Shift electric load here	57.59
0.03293	159.79	0	0	True	-	-	32.96
0.03293	206.35	13.60	0	True	-	-	0.00
0.03293	223.05	30.30	0	True	-	-	0.00
0.04126	238.37	45.63	0	True	-	-	0.00
0.04417	220.33	27.59	0	False	-	-	0.00
0.04495	176.13	0	0	False	-	-	16.62
0.04417	158.19	0	0	True	-	-	34.56
0.04495	88.81	0	0	False	-	-	103.94
0.0454	50.41	0	0	False	-	-	142.34
0.04417	7.02	0	0	False	-	-	185.73
0.04417	0.00	0	11.04	True	sell surplus energy	-	203.79
0.02478	0.00	0	20.55	False	Cover the energy surplus	Shift electric load here	213.29
0.04417	0.00	0	11.91	False	Cover the energy surplus	-	204.66
0.02549	0.00	0	20.52	True	sell surplus energy	-	213.26
0.02478	0.00	0	24.17	True	sell surplus energy	-	216.92
0.02543	20.06	0	0	True	-	Shift electric load here	172.69
0.04658	43.78	0	0	True	-	-	148.96
0.04719	50.69	0	0	True	-	-	142.06
0.04417	48.92	0	0	True	-	-	143.83
E^*_{dem}	192.7485942						
Percentile Peak							
70							
75							
80							
85							
90							
95							

Figure 68. Inference rule peak strategy

In order to quantify the effect of the inference rule the Load factor for the $(E_{dem}-E_{gen})^+$ daily profile, with and without the application of inference rule, is calculated (Figure 69- Figure 70). If the DMS strategies can be implemented as suggested by inference rule the load factor increases from 0,344 to 0,419. Moreover, a calculation of the economic income related to the selling of energy is carried out.

Power demand [kW]	(Edem-Egen) ⁺ [kWh]	hourly Energy sold (peak) [kWh]	hourly surplus income (peak) [€]	hourly Energy used (peak) [kWh]	Cost saving (peak) [€]	hourly Income + cost saving [€]
58.64	50.08	0	0	0	0	0
60.51	51.68	0	0	0	0	0
71.50	61.07	0	0	0	0	0
96.59	81.65	0	0	0	0	0
160.35	135.16	0	0	0	0	0
189.60	159.79	0	0	0	0	0
255.77	206.35	0	0	0	0	0
265.98	223.05	0	0	0	0	0
288.19	238.37	0	0	2.89	0.12	0.12
290.68	220.33	0	0	23.01	1.02	1.02
261.10	176.13	0	0	75.87	3.41	3.41
340.38	158.19	0	0	126.63	5.59	5.59
301.25	88.81	0	0	163.79	7.36	7.36
273.65	50.41	0	0	188.59	8.56	8.56
270.68	7.02	0	0	220.39	9.73	9.73
259.90	0.00	11.04	0.55	190.52	8.42	8.97
248.37	0.00	20.55	0.45	168.96	4.19	4.64
230.13	0.00	11.91	0.48	154.42	6.82	7.30
113.36	0.00	20.52	0.82	125.21	3.19	4.01
57.97	0.00	24.17	0.97	49.50	1.23	2.19
59.18	20.06	0	0	30.47	0.77	0.77
57.59	43.78	0	0	5.39	0.25	0.25
59.90	50.69	0	0	0.46	0.02	0.02
59.90	50.69	0	0	0	0	0
Load factor	0.344		3.27		60.69	63.95

Figure 69. Load factor without considering the application of inference rule

Power demand [kW]	(Edem-Egen) ⁺ [kWh]	hourly Energy sold (peak) [kWh]	hourly surplus income (peak) [€]	hourly Energy used (peak) [kWh]	Cost saving (peak) [€]	hourly Income + cost saving [€]
58.64	50.08	0	0	0	0	0
60.51	51.68	0	0	0	0	0
71.50	82.23	0	0	0	0	0
96.59	81.65	0	0	0	0	0
160.35	156.32	0	0	0	0	0
189.60	159.79	0	0	0	0	0
255.77	192.75	0	0	0	0	0
265.98	192.75	0	0	0	0	0
288.19	192.75	0	0	2.89	0.12	0.12
290.68	192.75	0	0	23.01	1.02	1.02
261.10	176.13	0	0	75.87	3.41	3.41
340.38	158.19	0	0	126.63	5.59	5.59
301.25	88.81	0	0	163.79	7.36	7.36
273.65	50.41	0	0	188.59	8.56	8.56
270.68	7.02	0	0	220.39	9.73	9.73
259.90	0.00	11.04	0.55	190.52	8.42	8.97
248.37	21.16	20.55	0.00	189.50	4.70	4.70
230.13	0.00	0.00	0.00	166.32	7.35	7.35
113.36	0.00	20.52	0.82	125.21	3.19	4.01
57.97	0.00	24.17	0.97	49.50	1.23	2.19
59.18	41.22	0	0	30.47	0.77	0.77
57.59	43.78	0	0	5.39	0.25	0.25
59.90	50.69	0	0	0.46	0.02	0.02
59.90	50.69	0	0	0	0	0
Load factor	0.419		2.34		61.72	64.06

Figure 70. Load factor considering the application of inference rule

3.8.3 Impact of the action plan to the SCEAF indicators

In the following tables an analysis of the indicators optimized through the specific action plan is presented.

1st Pillar: Political Field of Action

Indicator	Description	Result
1.4	Medium term results for CO ₂ reduction in Municipal Buildings	Decrease of CO ₂ emissions
1.6	Medium term results for renewable energy sources in the final use in Municipal Buildings	Increase of renewable energy in the final use mix

2nd Pillar: Energy and Environmental Profile

Indicator	Description	Result
2.2	Percentage reduction of fossil fuels	Increase of renewables in energy mix, leading to a percentage decrease of fossil fuels
2.3	Average CO ₂ emission factor	Increase of renewables in energy mix, leading to a lower average emission factor
2.4	Renewable Energy Sources (RES) production intensity	Increase of renewables in energy mix

3rd Pillar: Related Infrastructures and ICT

Indicator	Description	Result
3.3	Forecasting systems	Additional forecasting system used within the building
3.5	Cost reduction for energy needs (gas, petroleum and electricity) in the municipal building	Increase of renewables in energy mix, leading to a decrease of fossil fuels use, hence to the avoidance of costs of fuel purchase

3.9 Action Plan 7: Scheduling the battery use towards peak shaving and energy cost optimization

3.9.1 Description of data and building partitioning

Inference Rule 9: Peak shaving towards energy cost optimization, is the basis of this Action Plan, where the main goal of the DSS is to detect, schedule and propose on daily basis a redistributed energy demand in order to minimize energy cost, mainly through peak shaving.

Inference Rule 8: Determination of the energy source to cover the demand, considering battery charging, RES production and the grid, can be used in systems able of storing and producing energy to schedule optimally the electricity storage, simulate the energy flows of the system and assist the implementation of inference rule 9.

However, both the inference rules and their suggestions refer to the upcoming week, relative forecasts must be provided for a set of variables. This mainly includes forecasting the total electricity consumption and the energy production (photovoltaic plants, CHP etc.) of the network, since weather forecasting is a prerequisite. The rest of the energy flows (flows from and to the batteries and the main grid) can then be estimated by applying the inference rule 8 to the provided forecasts. As described in D3.2, PV production and electricity consumption are effectively forecasted for each hour of the day individually using a unique MLR model per pilot building. In the latter case, additional models have been developed to predict electricity consumption for working and non-working days separately. This is mainly done in order to better model the influential effect of each time on the dependent variable, leading to increased accuracy, insignificant bias and robust performance.

According to the methodological framework proposed in D3.2, PV and electricity consumption MLR models were built for the pilot case of the Savona Campus, the pilot building where a hybrid system including both RES installations (PV plant and CHP) and a storage mechanism exists, and both the inference rules can be accordingly applied.

Energy prices are also predicted on monthly basis using ARIMA models. The differences between the prices of the different charging zones are calculated and then a variety of ARIMA models are estimated and applied on the created data to fit forecasting models. Using an information criteria (AIC) the most appropriate of these models is chosen and used to define which hours are the least expensive during the day.

The Savona Campus Pilot Case

In order to estimate the MLR model of the Savona Campus, a training sample of four months (3338 hours of non-zero and missing measurements) from 1st January 2014 to 22th April 2015 was used. The historical data include hourly observations for the local weather conditions, the electricity production of the RES and the electricity consumption of the Campus. The energy data were collected by the on-site monitoring system of the Campus, while the weather data were mined by the database of a nearby weather station. Monthly energy prices were also available from Jan 2010 to Oct 2015. A list of the collected variables is presented in the Table 13.

Table 14. Input data and source of acquisition for the Savona Campus

Input Data	Measurement units	Source	Spatial scale
Energy consumption	kWh	On-site monitoring system	Entire building
PV production	kWh	On-site monitoring system	Entire building
CHP production	kWh	On-site monitoring system	Entire building
Battery storage	kWh	On-site monitoring system	Entire building
Electricity from/to grid	kWh	On-site monitoring system	Entire building
Temperature	°C	Local weather station (tbc)	-
Humidity	-	Local weather station (tbc)	-
Pressure	Pa	Local weather station (tbc)	-
Wind Direction Degrees	-	Local weather station (tbc)	-
Solar Radiation	W/m ²	Local weather station (tbc)	-
Dew point	°C	Local weather station (tbc)	-
Wind Speed	Km/h	Local weather station (tbc)	-
Month	-	DSS Engine	-
Hour	-	DSS Engine	-
Day	-	DSS Engine	-
Type of Day	-	DSS Engine	-
Energy prices	€	Electricity provider website	-

As an example, the predicted electricity consumption and PV production (red lines) compared to the actual values (black lines) for 168 random and continuous observations (duration of one week) of the Savona data set, is illustrated in Figure 71. Given those forecasts (weather forecasts were also available), the electricity from and to the grid and the batteries can be estimated using the inference rule 8.

Figure 71: The predicted (red lines) and the original (black lines) values of the electricity consumption (upper left) and the PV production (upper right) for a random week of the Savona Campus data set. Given those forecasts, the electricity from/to the grid and the batteries is estimated, as seen in the last plot.

After the estimation of the energy demand from the main grid, the inference rule 9 can be applied to redistribute loads appropriately and minimize the energy cost. The suggested changes for a duration of two continuous random weeks (336 hours) are displayed in Figure 72. In the plot on the left the adjusted load can be examined, while in the plot on the right the changes arising to the electricity bought-sold to the main grid.

Figure 72: The created (red lines) and the original (blue lines) values of the electricity load and demand from the main grid after the implementation of the shifts

At this point we note that the Campus of Savona buys energy in three different energy prices, as shown in Figure 73: F1, F2 and F3. Usually F3 is cheaper than F2, which is cheaper than F1. However, this is not always the case since at some rare occasions, and especially in summer months, F1 may be cheaper than F2. This is why energy prices forecasting is vital in the specific action plan. The available energy prices data set is presented in Figure 74.

Figure 73: Charging zones of the Savona Campus

The bill is calculated each month by the following equation which includes a fixed cost, a cost based on total electricity consumption and losses, a cost based on the electricity consumed per charging zone and a peak penalty:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Energy Cost} = & [91,65 \\
 & +1,04 \times \text{EnergyF1} \times \text{PriceF1} \quad \rightarrow \text{Fixed Cost} \\
 & +1,04 \times \text{EnergyF2} \times \text{PriceF2} \quad \left. \begin{array}{l} \\ \end{array} \right\} \text{Energy Consumption Cost} \\
 & +1,04 \times \text{EnergyF3} \times \text{PriceF3} \\
 & +2,74 \times \text{Peak (monthly)} \quad \rightarrow \text{Peak Penalty} \\
 & + (0,00988 + 0,09117) \times \text{TotalEnergy} + 0,0151 \times 4,66174 \times \text{TotalEnergy}/100 \quad * 1,22 \\
 & \underbrace{\hspace{15em}}_{\text{Losses}}
 \end{aligned}$$

The inference rule optimizes peak shaving based on the formula above and reduces energy cost by reducing the peaks (minimizing the penalty) and moving loads to cheaper zones.

Figure 74: Energy prices per charging zone from Jan 2011 to Oct 2015

3.9.2 Application to a case study

Savona Campus Pilot Case

The main contribution of the presented action plan is that the energy manager is informed in advance about the electricity that is expected to be sold or bought in the following week through a detailed hourly report including the energy flows of the hybrid system he is responsible of, while a list of suggestions can be provided in order to reduce the energy cost of the facility through battery optimization and optionally peak shaving.

The abovementioned features are of high importance since the majority of the “smart” systems performing relative actions are based only on on-site automations and no relative information is provided before any decision has been already taken. Thus, in practice, any programming and management of the system is becoming complicated and therefore insufficient. Moreover, since the heuristics applied optimize the monthly energy cost of the building, better results can be achieved compared with other algorithms optimizing the energy cost just for the upcoming day(s).

The OPTIMUS DSS will provide an option regarding whether the user can apply changes to the energy demand of the Campus (and at which extent) and then optimize battery use based on the corresponding inference rule. In case that such changes are not applicable, battery optimization is directly applied to the original PV and energy demand predictions. This will be the default case for the examined pilot since, as indicated, at present no relative actions will be possible in practice. This is mainly given that the energy manager of the Campus does not have the power to impose a given behaviour to the University Courses or to the private Companies working in the Campus. Furthermore, as the energy manager does not currently have visibility of the various loads of the buildings, he/she could not discriminate well the cause and the effect of each load and suggested action. Only a few number of meters have recently be installed for a couple of buildings, but they are still accessed by the energy provider and not directly by the energy manager. In this respect, although the action

plan is generalized for buildings with shiftable loads, the pilot building will take full advantage only from the battery optimization inference rule of the system.

The action plan and the relative inference rules are applied through R scripts developed accordingly and customized for the specific case-study. This includes the construction of tailor made prediction models (PV and CHP production, energy demand and energy prices) and the optimization of the whole process based on the charging policy of the electricity provider of the Campus, as presented in section 3.7.2. The implemented inference rule uses the storages of the Campus as manageable loads for peak shaving, which can be summarized as follows:

- *Automated storage*: The batteries of this storage system are rated to 141 kW, from which 105 kW can be effectively used for the action plan and 36 kW is their minimum charge point. The system is under the full control of the EMS and can be programmed to operate automatically based on the DSS suggestions.
- *Manual storage*: This system, which is based on Li-ion technology and rated about 25 kWh and 50 kW, has been recently installed to the Campus and cannot be controlled by the EMS automatically yet. AT present a manual operation is only possible and some effort is needed in order to schedule it and deal with relative communication problems. In this respect, and till addressing the abovementioned problems, during the first phase of its operation the DSS will implement the inference rules based only on the capabilities of the automated storage system.

3.9.3 Impact of the action plan to the SCEAF indicators

In the following tables an analysis of the SCEAF indicators optimized through the specific action plan is presented.

1st Pillar: Political Field of Action

Indicator	Description	Result
1.4	Medium term results for CO ₂ reduction in Municipal Buildings	Decrease of CO ₂ emissions
1.5	Medium term results for renewable energy sources in the final use in Municipal Buildings	Increase energy used from RES

2nd Pillar: Energy and Environmental Profile

Indicator	Description	Result
2.3	Average CO ₂ emission factor	The total energy consumption is decreased (denominator), as well as the proportion of each energy carrier in the mix.

3rd Pillar: Related Infrastructures and ICT

Indicator	Description	Result
3.3	Forecasting systems	Additional forecasting system used within the building
3.5	Cost reduction for energy needs (gas, petroleum and electricity) in the municipal building	Decrease of energy consumption, leads to the avoidance of costs of fuel purchase

4 Inference rules implementation

The inference rules suggest action plans to the end-user by analyzing the forecasting data from the prediction models developed in Deliverable 3.2 *Analysis tools to process data and inference rules*).

The inference rules have been implemented following two approaches. For complex rules a Rapidminer process –which has been published as web services using RapidAnalytics²– has been implemented and for the simple rules a PHP script have been coded.

The following sections contains two examples of a rule implementation, one for each approach.

4.1 Implementation of a inference rule as a Rapidminer process

An example of an inference rule implemented as a Rapidminer process is the number 5, the PV Maintenance. This inference rule is based on a model designed to detect differences between predicted and actual values from the renewable energy production systems when they exceeds the 5% (accepted error). The inference rules have been implemented as an R script which has been encapsulated as a RapidAnalytics process likewise the prediction models described in Deliverable 3.2. The process includes operators to ask the semantic service historical data needed to calculate the rules (Number 1 in Figure 75) and to run the R script with the inference rules (Number 2 in Figure 75).

Figure 75. *RapidAnalytics process to implement Inference rule 5: PV maintenance*

The process has been published as a Web service and is invoked from the PHP classes of the DSS environment in order to provide daily alerts for a seven-day window. The service returns an XML providing the number of day (1, 2, 3 ...7) and “1” or “0” whether there are an alert or not for each day, according to the range of days provided in the call. Thereby, according to these daily outputs from the service, a message is shown for each day notifying the end-user if there was a problem with the RES (Renewable Energy Systems) energy production performance. See Deliverable 3.5 which include the internal architecture of the OPTIMUS DSS and the interrelations of the different modules including the inference rules.

² <http://sourceforge.net/projects/rapidanalytics/>

4.2 Implementation of the inference rule as PHP classes

An example of an inference rule implemented as PHP classes is the number 6, Scheduling of the sale/consumption of the electricity produced through the PV system. In this rule, the end-users can select one of the three strategies available: Green, Finance and Peak. According to the strategy selected, a suggestion is inferred applying the corresponding calculation. The input data needed for calculate the inference rules are: selling/purchase prices, energy production, and energy consumption which are stored in database. Moreover, two constants are needed: the energy threshold for daily penalty and percentage for the energy demand. Both constants are defined by the DSS administrator. Thereby, end-users are able to check suggestions inferred from these rules (e.g. “sell the energy produced” or “consume the energy produced” or “try to shift electrical loads”) for each hour.

To facilitate the visualization of proposed actions according to these strategies, suggestions obtained from inference rules are grouped defining different schedules (e.g. 14:00 to 16:00 → sell all the energy produced).

5 Nomenclature

Symbols

A	area	m^2
E, Q	energy	J, Wh
f	surface area factor	-
Φ	heat flux	W
G	mass flow rate	kg/h
h	heat transfer coefficient, enthalpy	W/(m^2K), J
H	heat loss coefficient	W/K
M	metabolic rate	W/ m^2
P	power	W
P	price	euro
pa	water vapour partial pressure	Pa
θ	temperature	$^{\circ}C$
R	thermal resistance	(m^2K)/W
τ	time constant	h
t	Time	h, day
v	velocity	m/s
V	volume	m^3
W	Effective mechanical power	W/ m^2

Subscripts

a	air
cl	clothing
cl	cooling
d	daily
dem	demand
des	design
e	external
f	floor
gen	generation
H	heating
i	internal
max	maximum
mix	mixing
mn,m	mean
n	neutrality, net
nd	need

o	operative
r	radiant, running
ret	recirculating
sup	supply
tr	threshold

6 References

Technical standards

EN ISO 7730 (2005), "Ergonomics of the thermal environment - Analytical determination and interpretation of thermal comfort using calculation of the PMV and PPD indices and local thermal comfort criteria".

EN ISO 13790 (2004), Thermal performance of buildings - Calculation of energy use for space heating

EN 15251 (2007), "Indoor environmental input parameters for design and assessment of energy performance of buildings- addressing indoor air quality, thermal environment, lighting and acoustics", CEN, Brussels.

Books

American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE) (2010), "Thermal environmental conditions for human occupancy", ASHRAE Standard 55-2010.

Nicol JF, Kessler MRB. Perception of comfort in relation of weather and indoor adaptive opportunities. ASHRAE Transactions, 1005-1017, 1998.

Wargocki P et al. Indoor climate and productivity in offices. Rehva guidebook. Finland: Forssan Kirjapaino Oy, 2006.

de Dear RJ, Brager GS, Cooper D. Developing an Adaptive Model of Thermal Comfort and Preference. ASHRAE RP-884 Final Report. American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air Conditioning Engineers, 1997.

Articles

Yang Z., Burcin B., The coupled effects of personalized occupancy profile based HVAC schedules and room reassignment on building energy use, Energy and Buildings, Volume 78, April 2014, Pages 113-122

Adamopoulou A. A., Tryferidis A. M., Tzovaras D. K. A context-aware method for building occupancy prediction. Energy and Buildings, Volume 110, 2016, Pages 229-244.

Klein L., Kwak J., Kavulya G., Jazizadeh F., Becerik-Gerber B., Varakantham P., Tambe M. Coordinating occupant behaviour for building energy and comfort management using multi-agent systems, *Automation in Construction*, Volume 22, 2012, Pages 525-536.

D'Oca S., Hong T. Occupancy schedules learning process through a data mining framework, *Energy and Buildings*, Volume 88, 2015, Pages 395-408.

Mahdavi A., Tahmasebi F. Predicting people's presence in buildings: An empirically based model performance analysis, *Energy and Buildings*, Volume 86, 2015, Pages 349-355.

McCartney K, Nicol JF. Developing an adaptive control algorithm for Europe. *Energy and Buildings*, Volume 34, Issue 6, July 2002, Pages 623-635.

Beizae, A., Firth, S. K. (2011), A Comparison of Calculated and Subjective Thermal Comfort Sensation in Home and Office Environment, *Proceedings of Conference: People and Buildings (MC2011)*, London, 23 September 2011.

Roach P., Bruno F., Belusko M. (2013), Modelling the cooling energy of night ventilation and economiser strategies on façade selection of commercial buildings, *Energy and Buildings*, Volume 66, November 2013, Pages 562–570

Seem J.E., House J.M., Development and evaluation of optimization-based air economizer strategies, *Applied Energy*, Volume 87, Issue 3, March 2010, Pages 910–924

Gang Wang, Li Song, An energy performance study of several factors in air economizers with low-limit space humidity, *Energy and Buildings*, Volume 64, September 2013, Pages 447–455